

MAtchUP

D2.26: New citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia

WP 2, T 2.7.2

Date of document

September 2019 (M24)

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MAtchUP - SCC-1-2016-2017

Innovation Action – GRANT AGREEMENT No. 774477

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement N°774477

Technical References

Project Acronym	MAtchUP
Project Title	MAximizing the UPscaling and replication potential of high level urban transformation strategies - MAtchUP
Project Coordinator	Ernesto Faubel Ayuntamiento de Valencia efaubel@valencia.es
Project Duration	1 October 2017 – 30 September 2022 (60 Months)

Deliverable No.	D2.26
Dissemination Level	PU ¹
Work Package	WP 2 - Demonstration in Valencia
Task	T 2.7.2 - Citizens' engagement and empowering
Lead beneficiary	7 (KVEL)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	1 (VAL), 2 (LNV), 7 (KVEL), 23 (ICE)
Due date of deliverable	30 September 2019
Actual submission date	25 September 2019
Estimated person-month for deliverable	17,20 (+18 for D2.27)

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Version	Person	Partner	Date
0.1	Francisco Azorín Isabel González Barbara Branchini	KVEL	7 August 2019
0.2	Francisco Azorín Isabel González	KVEL	17 August 2019
0.3	José Fuentes	LNV	3 September 2019
0.4	Barbara Branchini Alba Matamoros	KVEL	3 September 2019
1.0	Barbara Branchini	KVEL	9 September 2019
1.1	Eser Karakaya	SAM	16 September 2019
Final	Barbara Branchini	KVEL	19 September 2019

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CC	Communication Campaign
CE	Citizens' Engagement
Dn.n	Deliverable and numbers
DG	Driving Group
EC	European Commission
IAP2	International Association for Public Participation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
Mnn	Month and number
ToC	Table of Content
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VLC	Valencia
WS	Workshop
WP	Work Package

0 Abstract

This report constitutes Deliverable “D2.26: New citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia – 2nd version”, which is the main outcome of Task “T2.7.2: Citizens' engagement and empowering”. This report is the updated version of Deliverable “D2.12: New citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia – 1st version”, released in September 2018 (M12), while the final versions of it (i.e. D2.27) will be delivered in September 2020 (M36).

The aim of D2.12 was to design the conceptual framework and the strategy for the new citizens' engagement (Chapter 1 and 2), based on the analysis of the existing infrastructure, processes and relevant stakeholders for the public participation at the city and district level (Chapter 3) and the selection of suitable resources, key actors and the MAtchUP infrastructure for the citizen engagement (Chapter 4). Those chapters were therefore maintained unchanged in this report.

The **aim of D2.26** is to report the main outputs of the new citizens' engagement strategies put in place during M12-M24, and therefore the set-up of participatory bodies is reported as an **addendum to Chapter 4** and duly highlighted as such.

Furthermore, the action plan (**Chapter 5**), briefly drafted in D2.12, is now fully detailed in terms of action priorities, action plans and deployed activities. The main results and any update will be further reported within D2.27.

Similarly, while the communication measures were defined in D2.12 (Chapter 6), their deployment during the period M1-M24 is reported in this document (**Chapter 6.1**).

General considerations based on the experience of the first two years of implementation are included in **Chapter 7**. Any additional channel and measure of public participation, together with the preliminary results and conclusions on the new citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia will be included into the updated versions of this Deliverable (i.e. D2.27).

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and target group

The purpose of this report "D2.26: New citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia – 2nd version", is to describe the citizen engagement strategy that will be deployed in the Valencia demonstration site (i.e. the district of Poblats Marítims) under the MAtchUP project. This strategy is the main outcome of Task "T2.7.2: Citizens' engagement and empowerment". This report is the updated version of Deliverable "D2.12: New citizens' engagement strategies in Valencia – 1st version", released in September 2018 (M12) while the final versions of it (i.e. D2.27) will be delivered in September 2020 (M36).

The MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy has been deployed following a four-steps process including ecosystem analysis, diagnosis, action plan and communication. The strategy is based, in fact, on the analysis of the existing infrastructure, processes and relevant stakeholders for the public participation at the city and district level. The selection of suitable resources and key actors from civil society, business and industry, research and education allows to benefit from synergies and to avoid an overlapping of measures or citizens overburden. The action plan then builds on the existing resources and relevant actors and designs the participatory activities according to the level of participation entailed by the MAtchUP interventions in Valencia. The MAtchUP infrastructure for the citizen engagement as well as the communication measures are defined.

1.2 Contribution of partners

The **TABLE 1** depicts the main contributions from participant partners in the development of this deliverable.

Participant short name	Contributions
KVEL	Task and deliverable responsible party. Table of Content (ToC), Chapter 1 (Introduction), Chapter 2 (MAtchUP citizens' engagement process, Chapter 3 (Ecosystem analysis), Chapter 4 (Diagnosis), Chapter 5 (Action Plan), Chapter 6 (Dissemination & Communication Plan), Annex
ICE	Input for ToC of Chapter 6
LNV	Input for Chapters 4 and 6

Table 1. Contribution of partners

1.3 Relation to other activities in the project

The **TABLE 2** depicts the main relationship of this deliverable to other activities (or deliverables) developed within the MAtchUP Project and that should be considered along with this document for further understanding of its contents.

Deliverable Number	Relation
D1.1	D1.1 defines the Citizen Engagement approach followed in MAtchUP.
D1.2	D1.2 describes the approach, methodology, infrastructures and processes for capacity building and citizen engagement activities followed in MAtchUP.
D1.7	The findings from this D2.12 and the developed Action Plan will be the basis for further discussions and strategy development related to citizen engagement in the Smart City Strategic Plan for Valencia.
D1.14	The findings from this D2.12 and the developed Action Plan will be an input for the Valencia Replication Plan.
D2.12	D2.26 is the updated version of D2.12 and it reports the deployment in Valencia of the new citizens' engagement strategies designed within D2.12. D2.12 represents therefore the conceptual and methodological framework of D2.26.
D2.x	The strategy for public participation developed will accompany the whole MAtchUP actions implementation process at the Valencia demo-site.
D7.x	The strategy developed in Chapter 6 for publication, participation will go hand in hand with international projects to support the implementation processes of sustainable Action Plans of other cities.
D5.7	The social evaluation will facilitate the monitoring and assessment of the citizen engagement strategy and both D2.12 and D5.7 will provide an evidence-based ground for future experiences and public participation strategies.
D8.11	The strategy developed for public participation will go hand in hand with local and project-wide dissemination and communication activities.

Table 2. Relation to other activities in the project

2 MATCHUP Citizens' engagement process

We understand **citizen engagement** as a process of institutional and citizens' transformation. The participation of the quadruple helix of open innovation is therefore essential.

Figure 1. Quadruple helix of open innovation

The process of citizen engagement entails different **levels of public participation** (Inform, Involve, Consult, Collaborate and Empower), depending on the characteristics of the actions planned in a given programme, plan or project.

	INCREASING LEVEL OF PUBLIC IMPACT				
	INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	EMPOWER
GOAL	To provide balanced and objective information in a timely manner.	To obtain feedback on analysis, issues, alternatives and decisions.	To work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.	To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.	To place final decision-making in the hands of the public.
PROMISE	"We will keep you informed"	"We will listen to and acknowledge your concerns."	"We will work with you to ensure your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the decisions made."	"We will look to you for advice and innovation and incorporate this in decisions as much as possible."	"We will implement what you decide."

Figure 2. Spectrum of Public Participation

Source: Vancouver Mayor's Engaged City Task Force. Final Report, 2014, based on the IAP2 Public Participation Spectrum.

Under the MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy, the level of participation required by the Lighthouse interventions is analysed, in order to determine the level of engagement actions required.

The **highest participation level** is the empowerment and it is reached through the involvement in the decision making and policies processes. A citizen engagement strategy has to cover three main dimensions in order to enable a real empowerment:

- Awareness about the action site
- Capacity building – at the individual and collective level
- Generation of a favourable environment allowing the development of an active and binding participation

These three dimensions will be covered under the four MAtchUP pillars: Energy, Mobility, ICT and Citizens.

Figure 3. MAtchUP Pillars

Along the Project several participatory activities are planned: under WP1 along the characterization and the strategic planning, under WP8 under the Communication and Dissemination activities, and, in the demo sites, along the citizens' engagement actions (WP2-4). The features of **participation, co-decision, social inclusion and synergies with existing initiatives** (for further details on these features, see D1.1, p. 16-17) shall nurture the MAtchUP processes, both at the city and the project level. The several participatory activities scheduled along the Project should be understood as a continuous process and the **synergies** among the citizens' engagement actions, and between them and the existing initiatives under the planning, demonstration and replication actions should be identified, put in value and strengthened.

In order to clarify the **common participatory environment**, the following figure ([FIGURE 4](#)) shows the citizens' engagement infrastructure and processes planned along the Project at different levels, allowing to conceptualize them as parts of one common framework.

Figure 4. MATCHUP Citizens' Engagement Strategies

The MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy will be deployed following a four-steps process, summarized in the following paragraphs and detailed in Chapters 3, 4 and 5, including:

1. Ecosystem analysis
2. Diagnosis
3. Action plan
4. Dissemination and communication

2.1 Ecosystem analysis

The initial phase of the Ecosystem Analysis includes gathering information on existing resources for the public participation in the city of Valencia both in terms of relevant infrastructure and strategies. Existing and planned resources and strategies that are complementary to the MAtchUP strategy are identified, in order to establish synergies and not to overlap. The collaboration with private initiatives working in line with the MAtchUP goals is encouraged, promoted and disseminated. The ecosystem analysis and diagnosis proceeds in parallel to the analysis of the city plans and indicators (WP1, City Advanced Characterization, Step 1) and they are mutually nurtured.

2.2 Diagnosis

The Diagnosis phase allows defining the contextual basis for the Engagement Action Plan. To this end, as a first step the existing virtual and F2F infrastructures suitable for MAtchUP at the city and district level are selected, based on the Ecosystem analysis performed (Chapter 3), together with relevant key alliances. Besides, recommendations based on the input collected within the *WS1.-Diagnosis Launch Workshop*, held in Valencia the 3rd of July 2018 under the WP1 activities (see D1.1), allow the fine-tuning of the engagement action plan. The level of participation required by the Lighthouse interventions is then analysed, in order to determine the level of engagement actions required under the Action Plan. The virtual and face to face infrastructure that have to be created in order to implement the engagement strategy (together with the existing ones) are finally designed.

2.3 Action plan

An action plan designs the desired scenario that the actors want to reach as an answer to the characteristics analysed; therefore, the action plan designed for the Valencian citizen engagement strategy is based on the Ecosystem analysis and the Diagnosis. This has to be an action-oriented timeline, identifying key available resources and key responsibilities. At the current time, the action plan has started and it is under development.

2.4 Dissemination and Communication

The main paths and features of the communication activities related to the citizen engagement strategy and according to the planning under WP8 and the Valencia Local Communication Desk are finally designed in this document. The full dissemination and

communication strategy are described under the D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan and the features of the Local Communication Desk further specified, where needed.

Communication and Dissemination activities related to citizen engagement started in September 2018. However, during the elapsed time since the beginning of the project, the city of Valencia has made a special effort to spread the project, focusing on what is it about and in which areas of innovative actions will be carried out and where. The detailed description of the communication activities is in Chapter 6 on Dissemination and Communication.

3 Ecosystem analysis

The aim of this section is to analyse the existing citizen engagement infrastructure and processes, in order to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of the MAtchUP new citizen engagement strategies in the city of Valencia. The analysis is performed at the city and the district level.

Figure 5 - District object of the analysis

The district object of the analysis is POBLATS MARITIMS (district number 11 marked in red) where Valencia interventions will be performed. It is integrated by five sub-districts:

- ❖ Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França
- ❖ Malva-Rosa
- ❖ Beteró
- ❖ Grau
- ❖ Nazaret

The district and its five sub-districts are analysed in the present document and will be the environment for the citizen engagement activities deployed.

3.1 Analysis of the existing citizen engagement infrastructure

In this epigraph we'll analyse the existing channels and sites available in the city and the district enabling the direct participation of citizens in the construction and implementation of policies, strategies and plans.

It is necessary to point out that the City Council of Valencia is - as of September 2018 - developing the regulation document that allows the implementation of the Citizen Participation Model of the City of Valencia. This model was designed together with the citizenship through a participatory process. This **regulation document** based on the new model will allow the development and implementation of a virtual and in-person infrastructure common to all districts of the city of Valencia.

3.1.1 Virtual

Virtual infrastructure such as online platforms, application software, collaborative channels having as a purpose the citizen engagement at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower), in the district and/or in the four MAtchUP pillars: Energy, Mobility, ICT, Social.

In the district, we do not find specific virtual spaces of participation so we will refer to the infrastructure on a city scale, identifying those elements that we will be able to use within the MAtchUP project.

This section does not include public services or information platforms that do not have the aim of active participation of citizens in decision-making processes.

3.1.1.1 #DecidimVLC

It is the platform in which is carried out the on-line participation of the citizenship of Valencia. This platform is based on the technology CONSUL, a tool developed by the City Council of Madrid in Open Source and adapted by the city Council of Valencia.

Figure 6. #DecidimVLC

Although the tool at this time is only used for the development of the "Citizen Consultation on Investments" (participatory budgets), it presents other features such as:

- Presentation and discussion of **Ideas**
- Presentation and support of **Citizen Proposals**
- Co-drafting of **Collaborative Legislation**

At the time of the ecosystem analysis (Sept 2018) the city council of Valencia was developing new functionalities for the "citizen participation portal". From the project MATCHUP will work with the managing service (Decentralization and Citizen Participation Service) to collaborate in its development.

The two following websites are informative, but they are relevant as they facilitate two cornerstones of any engagement process: transparency and information. On one side, the "Open Government" for the data access, visualization and download, and on the other side "Geoportal", allowing the data geopositioned visualization. Both platforms are managed by the Municipality of Valencia.

The "#decidimVLC" URL is: <http://decidimvlc.valencia.es>.

3.1.1.2 Open Government

The website allows the access, visualization and download of several data. The platform is structured in four sections, as follows:

1. Transparency
2. Good governance
3. Open data
4. Budget visualization

Figure 7. Open government website

The “Open Government” URL is: <http://gobiernoabierto.valencia.es/va/>.

3.1.1.2 Geoportal

The “Geoportal” allows the geopositioned visualization of data through interactive data of the Valencia municipality map, classified by area (Environment, Urban Planning, Tourism, Transport, Health, ...). Data on public services, such as public equipment and urban elements, or organizations and associations are also included.

Figure 8. GEOPORTAL website

The “Geoportal” URL is: <https://geoportal.valencia.es/home/>.

3.1.2 Face-to-face (F2F)

The face-to-face infrastructure is the governance infrastructure for the citizen engagement based in the district. These are spaces and participatory groups aimed at increasing the citizens' influence on the decision making in the four MAtchUP pillars: Energy, Mobility, ICT, Social. In the following paragraphs, the existing infrastructure is analysed and the spaces and participatory groups that can be used within the MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy are selected. The governance infrastructure is presented by domain: city and district.

3.1.2.1 City domain

The spaces and participatory groups that can be used in the district within the MAtchUP citizen engagement are marked with an asterisk *.

A. Sectoral Councils / *Consejos Sectoriales*

The sectoral councils are cross-territorial consultation bodies. In general, they meet twice a year while extraordinary meetings take place when required. For the purpose of this analysis, only the bodies active from 2015 are taken into consideration.

- **Social** Council of the city / *Consejo **Social** de la ciudad de València **
- **Food** Town Council / *Consejo **Alimentario** Municipal*
- Town Council of **Environment** / *Consejo Municipal de **Medio Ambiente** **
- Town Council of **Cooperation** / *Consejo Municipal de **Cooperación** **
- Local Council of **Immigration and Interculturality** / *Consejo Local de **Inmigración e Interculturalidad** **
- Town Council of **Social Action** / *Consejo Municipal de **Acción Social** **
- Town Council of **Women** / *Consejo Municipal de la **Mujer** **

B. District Councils (territorial) / *Consejos de Distrito (territoriales)*

The District Councils (Consejos de Distrito) include political and civil society representatives and they are the consultation bodies of the District Boards (Juntas de Distrito). The District Boards are local administrative structures, they don't manage own budget but administrative procedures such as the registration of inhabitants, travel cards, licences, among others. They are territorial bodies (i.e. each district has one) and they meet three times a year.

District Council of the District Board of / *Consejo de Distrito de la Junta de Distrito de:*

- Marítim ***
- Abastos**
- Ciutat Vella**
- Exposición**
- Patraix**
- Russafa**
- Trànsits**
- Pobles del Nord**
- Pobles del Sud**
- Pobles de l'Oest**

C. Working Groups (thematic in each territory) /

GRUPOS DE TRABAJO (temáticos en cada territorio).

Working groups on specific themes within the District Councils. They meet quarterly.

WGs of the District Council of **Marítim** *

- Urban planning, Mobility and Investments in Neighbourhoods *
- Social Welfare *
- Culture
- Cohesion and Citizen Protection *

WGs of the District Council of **Abastos**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighbourhoods
- Social Welfare
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Ciutat Vella**

- Urban planning and Mobility
- Social Welfare

WGs of the District Council of **Exposició**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighbourhoods
- Social Welfare and Health
- Culture and Education
- Economic Activities

WGs of the District Council of **Patraix**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighbourhoods
- Social Welfare
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Russafa**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighbourhoods
- Social Welfare
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Trànsits**

- Urban planning and Investments in Neighbourhoods
- Social Welfare and Citizen Security
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Pobles de l'Oest**

- Urban planning, Mobility and Investments in Neighbourhoods
- Social Welfare and Citizen Security
- Culture

WGs of the District Council of **Pobles del Nord**

WGs of the District Council of **Pobles del Sud**

D. Ad hoc F2F spaces

Working groups and participatory bodies may be created for specific processes or projects. Currently, the Municipality is mapping all the existing bodies. Once the mapping is finalized, we will select the bodies relevant for the district and the MATCHUP engagement strategy. These bodies are:

- TECHNICAL-POLITICAL TABLE / MESAS TÉCNICO - POLÍTICAS
- POLITICAL-CITIZEN TABLE / MESAS POLÍTICO - CIUDADANAS
- TECHNICAL-CITIZEN TABLE / MESAS TÉCNICO - CIUDADANAS

E. New spaces

The "citizen participation model of the city of València" plans the creation of further spaces for participation, which are therefore expected but not available at the moment. Some of them are considered relevant to the MATCHUP engagement strategy. They are:

- OBSERVATORY OF PARTICIPACION OF THE CITY OF VALENCIA /
OBSERVATORIO DE PARTICIPACIÓN DE LA CIUDAD DE VALENCIA
- OBSERVATORIES DISTRICT / OBSERVATORIOS DE DISTRITO *
- DISTRICT OFFICES OF CITIZEN INFORMATION /
OFICINAS DE ATENCIÓN CIUDADANA A NIVEL DE DISTRITO *

F. CONNECTA networks/ Redes Connecta (Las Naves - Innovation)

The CONECTA networks are aimed to generate networking communities among the main actors of the quadruple helix of innovation on the following five strategic sectors:

- MOBILITY *
- ENERGY AND WATER *
- AGRO-FOOD
- HEALTH AND HEALTHY CITY
- CREATIVE AND CULTURAL INDUSTRY

G. Other networks

- VIT EMPRENDE, a network promoted by the Employment and Entrepreneurship Foundation of the Municipality of Valencia, and aimed at bringing together the entrepreneurial ecosystem of the city.

H. "Parla amb Joan Ribó"

Open space where proposals, suggestions, petitions or complaints can be forwarded to the mayor and the municipal government. This space is established as an active listening mechanism with the purpose of improving the management of the city.

3.1.2.2 District domain

A. DISTRICT COUNCIL OF THE MUNICIPAL BOARD OF POBLATS MARITIMS / CONSEJO DE DISTRITO DE LA JUNTA DE DISTRITO DE MARÍTIM

Composition

President: Glòria Tello Company

Vice President: Sandra Gómez López

Secretary: María José Iranzo Iranzo

Working Groups linked to MATCHUP

Urban planning, Mobility and Investments in

- Neighbourhoods *
- Social Welfare
- Coexistence and Citizen Protection

3.3 Analysis of participatory processes and tools deployed in the district

The aim of this section is to analyse processes and tools for the participation implemented in the district in the last five years (starting from 2014).

Relevant processes on this regard were found in the sub-districts from Poblats Maritims District: Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França, Nazaret and Grau. Furthermore, the participatory process #DecidimVLC, managed at the city level, was also considered relevant for its impact on the district.

For each process, the following aspects were analysed: driving entity, used infrastructure, degree of public participation achieved (Inform, Involve, Consult, Collaborate, Empower), involved people, status, and evaluation outcomes.

3.3.1 Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França

The sub-district Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França is today one of the most remarkable urban areas of the city of Valencia. Historically, it has been a maritime neighbourhood with a strong identity character, characterized by its architectural and urban heritage, its variety of own traditions, population mixture and civic vitality. The neighbourhood has been the subject of urban aggression that has significantly deteriorated its image, both internally and as a city, generating a strong physical and social degradation.

Figure 9 - The subdistrict Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França

3.3.1.1 VA CABANYAL

Va Cabanyal was the participatory process developed in the sub-district of Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França for the elaboration of the Strategy for Sustainable and Integrated Urban Development (EDUSI), funded 50% by ERDF and 50% by the municipality. The aim of the strategy is the rehabilitation of the neighbourhood from a multidimensional approach that encompasses the physical, economic and social regeneration of the area.

Va Cabanyal followed a bottom up approach, with all the stakeholders invited to get involved in. Through this participatory process, neighbours, policy makers and economic stakeholders have brought together all their proposals to identify challenges and needs, drafting the necessary actions to succeed in the social and economic regeneration of the area.

Driving entity: Municipality of Valencia.

i. Used infrastructure

The process was structured around the following working groups:

- Driving Group (25-30 neighbours)

- Communication & Dissemination Working Group
- Technical & Political Working Group
- Monitoring Committee

Several participatory spaces were enabled, both virtual and F2F. The virtual spaces enabled were:

- ✓ Web (vacabanyal.org)
- ✓ Twitter (@VaCabanyal)
- ✓ E-mail (vacabanyal@gmail.com)

The F2F participatory spaces included the office where most working activities took place, interviews to relevant actors, and participatory workshops, as detailed below.

(1) *Va Cabanyal* Office: dissemination and work space.

(2) Interviews. Several interviews were performed with neighbours and experts. Besides, exploratory questionnaires were spread among neighbours and shops owners. The interviews and the questionnaires allowed to deepen the main issues of interest for the neighbourhood, prioritized along the analysis and diagnosis phases, to widen the participation channels and as an information/ data source on relevant themes.

(3) Workshops. Three large workshops open to participation were organized in order to involve citizens in the process of designing the urban strategy for the sub-district from the beginning. The workshops aimed at covering the three steps of the process, namely diagnosis, elaboration of proposals, prioritization and lines of action. Specific participatory activities were realized addressed to children (6-12yo), *Va Cabanyal Infantil*.

The working groups and participatory spaces detailed above collaborated in the process of strategy elaboration, structured along three progressive phases (see [FIGURE 7](#)).

- ✓ Analysis and diagnosis
- ✓ Elaboration of proposals
- ✓ Prioritization and lines of action

Furthermore, the strategy plans the creation of a Neighbourhood Office in charge of the coordination of the programmes and projects developing in the sub-district, setting the mechanisms for an efficient and binding citizen engagement.

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology used and the several open channels for participation, allowed the engagement at all levels, from the lowest to the highest. Each person, group or entity decided how they wanted to be involved, from registering to a mailing list to be informed (Inform), to participate in the spaces and activities of consultation (Consult), to be involved in the working groups (Involve), to collaborate in the driving group and in the decision-making workshops (Collaborate).

iii. People involved

Several groups and individuals were involved in the neighbourhood, including key actors from the quadruple helix, as shown in the Sociogram ([FIGURE 8](#)). Significant effort was dedicated to this end, in order to identify the relevant actors and to analyse the relationships among them, with the aim of ensuring the largest representativeness

across the neighbourhood. The neighbourhood has a strong associative and collaborative fabric, so that the participation levels had to be high.

iv. Status

Closed. Deploying period: September 2015 - December 2015.

v. Evaluation outcomes

An evaluation of the participatory process was performed, but it is not public.

None of the participatory spaces and channels developed under *Va Cabanyal* is currently active. See **FIGURE 10** and **FIGURE 11** for further details.

Figure 10. Va Cabanyal process

Several participatory spaces are enabled, both virtual and F2F. The virtual spaces enabled are:

- ✓ Web (<http://www.pecplaespecial.com>)
- ✓ Facebook (@PECPlaEspecial)
- ✓ E-mail (info@pecplaespecial.com)

The F2F participatory spaces include the office where most working activities take place, interviews with relevant actors, and participatory workshops and activities, as detailed below.

- (1) Participation Office: dissemination and work space.
- (2) Interviews: Several interviews are administered to neighbours and experts, in order to approach the context and set diagnosis lines and potential fields of action.
- (3) Workshops for decision making.
- (4) Info days for dissemination and training.
- (5) Participatory urban drifting, in order to collect subjective perspectives and perceptions on the urban environment.

The working groups and participatory spaces detailed above collaborate in the process of strategy elaboration, structured along three progressive phases, as shown in **FIGURE 12**:

- ✓ Information and diagnosis
- ✓ Pathways and strategies
- ✓ Preliminary proposal

Figure 12. PEC process

According to the participatory process outcome, the setup of the Local Office for the Integrated Management of the Renovation and PEC Implementation is expected. The

PEC local office would be in charge of designing the spaces and mechanisms for an efficient and binding citizen engagement, among other tasks.

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology and the several open channels for participation, allow the engagement at all levels, from the lowest to the highest. Each person, group or entity can decide how they want to be involved, from registering to a mailing list to be informed (Inform), to participate in the spaces and activities of consultation (Consult), to be involved in the working groups (Involve), to collaborate in the driving group and in the decision-making workshops (Collaborate).

iii. People involved

The involved public is the same identified within the Va Cabanyal sociogram, shown in the previous paragraph. In fact, the working area and the involved public coincide in the two processes, Va Cabanyal and PEC Cabanyal.

iv. Status

The participatory phase is closed.

Participatory phase: July 2017 - February 2018.

Public exposition and allegations: until October 2018.

v. Evaluation outcomes

No evaluations were performed on the process as of today.

None of the participatory spaces and channels developed is currently active, except the Monitoring Committee, in charge of the information to the public and answering the allegations during the public exposition legal process.

3.3.2 Nazaret

Figure 13 - The Nazaret sub-district

Nazaret is the southern sub-district of Poblats Marítims district. Its geographical location at the mouth of the Turia River has historically offered a privileged location with its own beach and surrounded by vegetable garden. This situation changes with the amplification of the Port, the construction of a multitude of infrastructures and the implementation of the logistics activities zone, since they completely isolate the neighbourhood from the rest of the city. The construction of the Formula 1 circuit makes the situation even worse and ended up stripping Nazaret of the assets it had.

3.3.2.1 Collaborative elaboration of the neighbourhood strategy

The Integrated Strategy for Nazaret is initiated by the Valencia Municipality in order to guide the pathways and actions to develop in the next years in the neighbourhood.

Accordingly, the municipality is planning similar participatory processes in other districts of the city, addressed to the elaboration of integrated strategies. This approach shifted the city model from a process of growth towards the periphery and related degradation of the agricultural area of the Huerta to a more sustainable rehabilitation aimed at the improvement of the living conditions in the urban environment instead.

Driving entity: Municipality of Valencia.

i. Used infrastructure

The participatory process is structured around the following working groups:

- Promoting Group (25-30 neighbours), including two sub-groups: associations and citizens.
- Thematic Working Groups: urbanism; housing and mobility; education, health and culture; cohesion, employment and economy.
- Technical Working Group, including the local administration staff in the neighbourhood, such as practitioners of the health centers, social workers, youth professionals, teachers, trainers, religious communities, and other entities of social work).
- Monitoring Committee, with representatives of the different demographic groups and the existing public and social resources.

Several participatory spaces are enabled, both virtual and F2F. The virtual spaces enabled are:

- ✓ Web (<http://www.estrategianatzaret.valencia.es>)

The F2F participatory spaces include interviews to relevant actors and participatory workshops and activities, as detailed below.

(1) Interviews. Several interviews are administered to neighbours and experts, in order to further clarify issues prioritized during the analysis and diagnosis phases, and to develop contents for the action plan.

(2) Workshops or open meetings for decision making, one for each phase of the process of strategy elaboration.

(3) Workshops dedicated to specific target groups (Roma, immigrants, youngsters, ...).

(4) Timelines.

The working groups and participatory spaces detailed above collaborate in the process of strategy elaboration, structured along three progressive phases:

- ✓ Participatory diagnosis
- ✓ Training
- ✓ Proposals, including action lines and actions

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology and the several open channels for participation, allow the engagement at all levels, from the lowest to the highest. Each person, group or entity can decide how they want to be involved, from registering to a mailing list to be informed (Inform), to participate in the spaces and activities of consultation (Consult), to be involved in the

working groups (Involve), to collaborate in the promoting group and in the decision-making workshops and open meetings (Collaborate).

iii. People involved

Representatives of the quadruple helix were involved: public administration, citizens, academia and business. Mechanisms and participatory channels were also put in place in order to address the cultural and social diversity of the neighbourhood and to avoid any undesired exclusion. The involved population is shown in the related sociogram (FIGURE 14).

Figure 14. Nazaret strategy sociogram

iv. Status

Closed. Deploying period: October 2016 - February 2017.

v. Evaluation outcomes

An evaluation of the participatory process was performed, but it is not public. None of the participatory spaces and channels developed is currently active. The Integrated Strategy for Nazaret has not been presented to the public so far.

3.3.3 Grau

Figure 15 - The Grao sub-district

The Grao sub-district is located in the center of the POBLATS MARITIMS, linked to the historic dock of the Port of Valencia. In the last decades it has suffered important transformations derived both from the expansion of the port and the construction of large urban infrastructures such as the bases of the America's Cup or the Formula 1 circuit. Currently, the Valencia City Council is developing a process of citizen appropriation and opening of the seafront of the port, reversing the privatization of public space resulting from the implementation of the infrastructure mentioned above.

3.3.3.1 "Marina voices" / "Veus de la Marina"

The participatory process "Veus de la Marina" is developed with the objective of collaboratively designing, together with citizens, the new toponyms and routes, as well as the new signage of the public spaces of La Marina de Valencia (esplanades, docks, streets, old foundations, etc.).

The aim is *to turn La Marina into a public space full of life, where citizens find a cultural and social reference and spend time for work and leisure.*

Driving entity: Consorcio Valencia 2007, composed by representatives of the Municipality of Valencia, the Valencian Regional Government and the National Government.

i. Used infrastructure

Several participatory spaces are enabled, both virtual and F2F. The virtual spaces enabled are:

- ✓ Web, not specific of the participatory process (www.lamarinadevalencia.com)
- ✓ E-mail (veusdelamarina@marinadevalencia.com)
- ✓ Online forms

The F2F participatory spaces include interviews to relevant actors and participatory workshops for the decision making, as detailed below.

(1) Interviews. Several interviews are administered to neighbours and experts as an approach to the local context and deepening of issues raised during the workshops.

(2) Workshops for decision making.

The participatory spaces detailed above collaborate in the process of strategy elaboration, structured along three progressive phases:

- ✓ Technical analysis and diagnosis. To this end, the following tools were used: field work and participant observation; interviews; online forms.

- ✓ Collective construction. To this end, the following tools were used: four thematic workshops, two for each theme: identity and public spaces, collective memory; workshops in the educational center CEIP Las Arenas; online forms.
- ✓ Implementation of the actions.

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology and the several open channels for participation, allow the engagement at all levels, from the lowest to the highest. Each person, group or entity can decide how they want to be involved, from registering to a mailing list to be informed (Inform), to participate in the spaces and activities of consultation (Consult), to be involved in the working groups (Involve), to collaborate in the promoting group and in the decision-making workshops and open meetings (Collaborate). The process was also a tool for empowering citizens, since the decisions taken were effectively implemented (Empower).

iii. People involved

The categories of actors involved are: neighbours, visitors, workers and entrepreneurs from La Marina. The detailed list of the people involved is not available.

iv. Status

Closed. Deploying period: April 2017 - May 2018.

v. Evaluation outcomes

Evaluations of the participatory process are not known.

The participatory spaces and channels developed are currently not active.

3.3.4 City domain

3.3.4.1 #DecidimVLC

Through the city platform #DecidimVLC several processes of participatory budgeting were implemented. However, the participatory processes were implemented at the district level across the city.

i. Used infrastructure

The process is structured around the web platform [www. Decidimvlc.valencia.es](http://www.Decidimvlc.valencia.es) and the working groups organized in the district.

The main participatory virtual spaces enabled are:

- ✓ Web (www.decidimvlc.valencia.es)
- ✓ Facebook (@decidimVLC)
- ✓ Twitter (@decidimVLC)
- ✓ E-mail (consultaciudadanadinversiones@valencia.es)

The district working group constitutes the F2F participatory space for this participatory process.

The working group and participatory spaces detailed above collaborate in the process structured along three progressive phases:

- ✓ Proposals and support

✓ Evaluation

✓ Ballot

ii. Achieved degree of participation

The methodology and the several open channels for participation, allow the engagement at different levels:

- Proposing investment projects individually or on behalf of an association
- Supporting the proposals presented
- Joining the District Working Groups, individually or on behalf of an entity/ association
- Voting

#DecidimVLC is an empowering tool since specific public investment is allocated on the decisions taken by citizens; the decisions taken are implemented. moreover, the tools available allow each person, group or entity to decide how they want to be involved, from following the website to be informed (Inform), to supporting proposals and/or voting (Consult), to be involved in the elaboration of proposals (Involve), to collaborate in the working groups or the collective proposals (Collaborate).

iii. People involved

The process is addressed to the inhabitants of the city of Valencia over the age of 16 years, and the participation mechanisms are put in place with this purpose.

iv. Status

Every year since 2015 (Calls 2015-2016 / 2016-2017 / 2017-2018 / 2018-2019).

v. Evaluation outcomes:

An evaluation of the participatory process was performed, but it is not public.

3.4 Analysis of key stakeholders

The stakeholders and services related to the city engagement strategy in the district relevant under the four MAtchUP pillars are mapped under this section. The several sources of information are taken into account for the purpose:

- Municipal register of associations
- Sociograms and lists of key actors developed within the participatory processes realized in the district (Va Cabanyal, PEC Cabanyal, Integrated Strategy for Nazaret, Marina's voices).
- Consultations with the key stakeholders and experts in the district

Key actors are identified within the following profiles according to:

I. THE QUADRUPLE HELIX MODEL OF OPEN INNOVATION

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION / PUBLIC SERVICES

PRIVATE SECTOR

CITIZENS AND CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS

RESEARCH AND UNIVERSITY

II. THE FOUR MATCHUP PILLARS

ENERGY

MOBILITY

ICT

SOCIAL

The key actors and services are listed in the following tables; other relevant actors and services located in the District are included in Annex I. Other relevant actors and services in the district.

3.4.1 Quadruple helix

3.4.1.1 Public Administration / Public Services

Municipal bodies

District Board of Marítimo / Junta de Distrito De Marítimo

District Council of Marítimo / Consejo de Distrito De Marítimo

Decentralization and Participation Service: Virginia Martín (Head of Service) / Servicio de Descentralización y Participación

MATchUP Project Manager: Ernesto Faubel, Providing Connection with the rest of Municipal Services Involved in MATchUP and its Representatives:

Innovation Department / Serv. Innovación
 Trade and Supply Department / Serv. Comercio y Abastecimiento
 Employment and Entrepreneurship Department / Serv. Empleo y Emprendimiento
 Social Welfare and integration Department / Serv. Bienestar social e Integración
 Urban Projects Department / Serv. Proyectos urbanos
 Infrastructure works Department / Serv. Obras de infraestructuras
 Housing Department / Serv. Vivienda
 Education Department / Serv. Educación -
 Sport Department and Municipal Sports Foundation / Serv. Deporte y Fundación Deportiva Municipal
 Circulation, Transport and its Infrastructures Department / Serv. Circulación, Transporte y sus Infraestructuras
 Cultural Heritage Department / Serv. Patrimonio cultural
 Cultural Resources Department / Serv. Recursos culturales
 Economic Promotion and Tourism Department / Serv. de Promoción económica y Turismo
 Information and Communication Technology Department (SERTIC) / Serv. Teconología de la Información y la Comunicación
 Environmental Quality Department / Serv. Calidad medioambiental

Plan Cabanyal Office: Vicent Gallart (Head of office)

AUMSA. Municipal Urban Performances / Actuaciones Urbanas Municipales S.A. Valencia

FOUNDATIONS:

Climate Change Foundation / Fundación Cambio Climático
 Employment Pact Foundation / Fundación Pacto por el Empleo

OBSERVATORIES

Climate Change Observatory / Observatorio del Cambio Climático
 Observatory for Employment / Observatorio para el empleo

LAS NAVES. Innovation center of Valencia

Regional bodies

GENERALITAT VALENCIANA (REGIONAL AUTHORITY):

Housing Department / Conselleria de Vivienda
 Education Department - ITACA System / Conselleria de Educación
 Sustainable economy and work / Conselleria de Economía Sostenible y Trabajo
 SERVEF - Valencian Service of occupation and formation / Servei Valencià d'Ocupació i Formació
 IVACE - Valencian Institute of Business Competition / Instituto Valenciano de la Competencia Empresarial

(IVE) VALENCIAN INSTITUTE OF BUILDING / INSTITUTO VALENCIANO DE LA EDIFICACIÓN

Public services: education, social and employment

	EDUCATION/ TRAINING	SOCIAL	EMPLOYMENT
CABANYAL-CANYAMELAR -CAP DE FRANÇA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEIP Las Arenas (primary) CEIP Serrería (primary) CAES Santiago Apóstol (private) (primary) Colegio Pureza de María (private) (primary) Colegio Chiner de Villaroya (private) (primary) Colegio Nuestra Señora del Rosario (private) (primary) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centro de Menores de El Cabanyal (young people) Centro Municipal de Personas Mayores de El Cabanyal (adults) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Valencia Activa. Oficina de Marítimo (employment)
NAZARET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEIP Juan Manuel Montoya (primary) CEIP Ausias March (primary) Colegio Nuestra señora de los Desamparados (private) (primary and secondary) Colegio Santa Magdalena Sofia (privado) (La Punta) (primary) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centro Municipal de Servicios Sociales de Nazaret (social services) Centro Especializado de Atención a Mayores de Nazaret (CEAM) (elderly people) Centro Municipal de Actividades Personas Mayores (CMAPM) (elderly people) Centro Municipal de Juventud de Nazaret (young people) 	
GRAU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IES Grao (secondary) IES Baleares (secondary) CEIP El Grao (primary) CEIP San José de Calasanz (primary) Colegio La Purísima (private) (primary) Colegio Trafalgar (private) (primary) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> COL.LAB de Las Naves (Business incubator of social innovation)
MALVARROSA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IES Isabel de Villena (secondary) CEIP Malvarrosa (primary) CEIP Ballester Fandos (primary) CEIP Blasco Ibáñez (primary) CEIP Cavite-Isla del Hierro (primary) Escuelas Pías Malvarrosa (private) (primary and secondary) Centro de Formación de Personas Adultas Malvarrosa (adults) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centro de Día de Jóvenes Malvarrosa (young people) Centro de Servicios Sociales de la Malvarrosa (social services) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Taller Prelaboral para Jóvenes Malvarrosa (employment workshop)
BETERÓ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IES Serpis (secondary) IES Cabanyal (secondary) 		

3.4.1.2 Private sector**BUSINESS ASSOCIATIONS**

Asociación de Comerciantes del Marítimo ACIPMAR
 Asociación de Vendedores del mercado de El Cabanyal.
 Asociación de Empresarios Playa de las Arenas

STARTUPS COL-LAB "LAS NAVES"

Ponverdeatuvecino

MATCHUP PARTNERS

ETRA
 WiTraC
 Kveloce I+D+i

OTHER BUSINESS

AEIOLUZ

OTHER INSTITUTIONS

La Marina de València
 Autoridad Portuaria

OTHER CENTERS

Lanzadera
 EDEM

3.4.1.4 Citizens and civil society organizations

	NEIGHBOURHOOD ASSOCIATIONS	OTHER ASSOCIATIONS	CITIZEN PLATFORMS	SELF-MANAGED SPACES	INITIATIVES
CABANYAL-....	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVV Cabanyal-Canyamelar AVV Pavimar AVV Llamósí-Remonta 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AMPA (parents) Colegio de Las Arenas Asociación de Jubilados y Pensionistas Cabañal (elderly) Asociación Amas de Casa Tyrius del Marítimo (women) Associació Brúfol (social) Ateneu Marítim (cultural/building) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salvem El Cabanyal Millorem El Cabanyal Cabanyal Reviu 15m Pobllats Marítims 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Espai Veïnal Cabanyal La Col·lectiva Cabanyal Horta CSOA La Fusteria Ateneo Libertario Espai Obert El Marítim 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cabanyal Intim Cabanyal Arxiu Viu CraftCabanyal Radio Escalante 329
NAZARET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVV Nazaret AVV Nazaret Unido 	<p><i>Employment</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVFEN (Asociación Valenciana para el Fomento de Empleo Natzaret) Proyecto Mare (fundación José María Haro) <p><i>Other</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asociación de Jubilados y Pensionistas Marítimo (elderly people) El Arca de Noé (social) Asociación U-Manos de Integración para el Desarrollo Educativo (education) Asociación Ágora Cultural (cultural) Asociación Àmbit y Albergue Espai (social) Associació de Dones Natzaret Portes a Fora (women) Grupo Scout Iter-Natzaret (young people) 	-	-	-
GRAU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVV Balears-Grau AVV Grau-Port 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asociación de Jubilados y Pensionistas del Puerto 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Litoral per al poble 15M Poblados Marítims 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Matraz 	
MALVARROSA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVV Amics de la Malva AVV Malvarrosa-Poblados Marítims 	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Malva Conviu 	-	-
BETERÓ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVV Beteró 				

3.4.1.5 Research and university

POLYTECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF VALENCIA / UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE VALÈNCIA (UPV)

Cátedra Transporte y Sociedad (UPV)
Cátedra Govern Obert (UPV)

UNIVERSITY OF VALENCIA / UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA (UV)

Cátedra Ciudad de València (UV)
IRTIC - Instituto Universitario de Investigación de Robótica y Tecnologías de la Información y Comunicación (UV)
INTRAS - Institut Universitari d'Investigació de Trànsit i Seguretat Viària (UV)

ITE. TECHNOLOGICAL INSTITUTE OF ENERGY / INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE LA ENERGÍA

3.4.3 MATCHUP Pillars

3.4.3.1 Energy

There have not been detected agents present in the district linked to Energy.

3.4.3.2 Mobility

- València Camina
- València en Bici
- Colecamins
- València per l'aire

3.4.3.3 ICT

There have not been detected agents present in the district linked to ICTs

3.4.3.4 Citizens

- Taula Solidaritat Malvarrosa (Comité Ciudadano Anti-Sida, Fundació Aixec, Fundació Dasyc, Associació Xarxa, Save The Children, Cooperació Social Universitaria , Fundació-Amigó, Asociación Ambient)
- Secretariado Gitano

4 Diagnosis

The Diagnosis phase, as [FIGURE 16](#) shows, allows defining the contextual basis for the Engagement Action Plan. To this end, as a first step, the existing virtual and F2F infrastructures suitable for MAtchUP at the city and district level are selected, based on the Ecosystem analysis performed (Section 3), together with relevant key alliances. Besides, recommendations based on the input collected within the WS1. Diagnosis Launch Workshop, held in Valencia the 3rd of July 2018 under the WP1 activities (see D1.1) allow the fine-tuning of the engagement action plan. The level of participation required by the Lighthouse interventions is then analysed, in order to determine the level of engagement actions required under the Action Plan. The virtual and face to face infrastructure that have to be created in order to implement the engagement strategy (together with the existing ones) are finally designed.

Figure 16 - Phases of the Diagnosis

- Selection of existing infrastructures and key alliances
- Recommendations
- Level of participation entailed by LH interventions
- MAtchUP virtual and F2F infrastructure

4.1 Selection of existing infrastructure

Based on the analysis of the existing infrastructure, the bodies and spaces of participation existing and relevant for the MAtchUP process are selected, both the institutional and the resulting from previous participatory processes. The infrastructure identified will be involved in the MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy (see [FIGURE 17](#)).

	CITY DOMAIN	DISTRICT DOMAIN
F2F	MUNICIPALITY Social Council Environment Council Cooperation Council Immigration and interculturality Council Social Action Council Women Council Marítim District Council WGs of the Marítim District Council (Urban planning, Social Welfare, Cohesion) District observatory	MUNICIPALITY Marítim District Council & WGs #DecidimVLC participatory budgeting
	LAS NAVES CONNECTA Mobility CONNECTA Energy & Water	
	VALENCIACTIVA VIT EMPRENDE	
	NOT AVAILABLE Ad hoc F2F spaces (under mapping process) District observatories (expected) District office of citizen information (expected)	NOT AVAILABLE Va Cabanyal participatory process infrastructure (not active) PEC participatory process F2F infrastructure (not active) PEC Monitoring Committee (Cabanyal-Canyamelar-Cap de França) (expected) Integrated Strategy for Nazaret participatory process infrastructure (not active)
VIRTUAL	MUNICIPALITY #DecidimVLC Open Government Geoportals	MUNICIPALITY PEC participatory process virtual infrastructure #DecidimVLC participatory budgeting

Figure 17. Relevant existing infrastructure

Moreover, key alliances are identified, based on the analysis of the key stakeholders. A sociogram is used as a tool to identify key alliances, their action sets and feasibility.

The district sociogram is currently under development.

This district sociogram will allow to visualize the degree of affinity with the project objectives of each stakeholder and its capacity to influence in this context. Moreover, once the agents are mapped, the sociogram will allow us to establish action sets that will gather agents with common positions as well as possible conflicts existing in the territory.

Finally, through the sociogram feasible alliances will be identified, both for strengthening their connection or managing conflicts, and further relevant actors, missed in previous processes, targeted.

4.2 Recommendations for action planning

Under the MAtchUP WP1, the Workshop WS1 Diagnosis Launch Workshop was held in Valencia the 3rd of July 2018 (M10) under the WP1 activities (see D1.1 and D1.4), aimed at analysing the existing city plans, related to citizen engagement, among others.

During the workshop, the Model for the Citizen Participation of the city of Valencia was analysed and Strengths and Weaknesses identified. This analysis is very relevant to the present engagement strategy, providing orientations on how to take advantage of the strengths and opportunities, and how to address and improve the weaknesses.

Along the MAtchUP engagement process the strengths and opportunities should be taken into account, and the weaknesses addressed in order to consolidate the strategy for the Project and further development.

STRENGTHS / Positive Aspects

Several participatory processes were implemented in the district, reaching medium- high participation levels (Involve and Collaborate), as mentioned above and as highlighted along the WS1.

- ✓ VA CABANYAL
- ✓ PEC CABANYAL
- ✓ Integrated Strategy for Nazaret
- ✓ Marina Voices
- ✓ DecidimVLC participatory budgeting in Poblats Maritims

Therefore, the public is mature for collaboration activities, but it has also high expectations and may suffer some burden proceeding from previous processes.

Besides, the previous participatory processes provided wide and relevant data and contents related to the planning in the district.

WEAKNESSES / Negative Aspects

The following weaknesses should be taken into consideration along the engagement strategy and the elaboration of the next regulatory model for the citizen participation.

- Lack of methodological frameworks to develop the mechanisms planned according to the participation model.
- Lack of evaluations (quantitative and qualitative) of some participatory processes and their public presentation.
- The evaluations carried out on previous processes and experiences are not identified and systematized.
- The evaluation and monitoring mechanisms are not defined.
- The territorial diagnoses of some districts are missing.
- Mechanisms or structures for the promotion of the internal participation among the personnel of the municipal administration are not designed (interdepartmental groups).
- The existing sectoral and inter-sectoral roundtables are not identified (in process).
- The implemented participation processes did not put in place measures or tools for the inclusion of people with some functional disability or with special necessities.

OPPORTUNITIES

The following opportunities should be taken into consideration along the engagement strategy and the elaboration of the next regulatory model for the citizen participation.

- Incorporation of "non-institutionalized" forms of participation.
- Introduction of other media for communication, engagement and transparency, such as the radio or TV (MATCHUP channel).
- New features for #DecidimVLC.
- Detailed development of digital information, participation and communication tools.

4.4 Degree of participation of the Demonstration actions

4.4.1 The participation levels model

The citizens' engagement process in Valencia will entail different levels of public participation, based on the Spectrum of Public Participation developed by the International Association of Public Participation (IAP2) (**FIGURE 18**).

The Spectrum ranges from low participation, where people are simply informed about the relevant problems and alternative solutions (on websites for example) to high, where they are empowered to take the final decision on the issue at hand (i.e., through citizen juries or referendums) (Ostling, 2016).

Figure 18. Levels of participation.

Source: <http://tompkinscountyny.gov/tccp/publicparticipation>.

The five levels proposed are discrete degrees, not steps, lacking a hierarchy between them: each level can be appropriate depending on the context and which stage is chosen depends on the characteristics of the planned actions. However, the further to the right on the Spectrum, the more influence citizens have over decisions, and the stages can be interpreted as being progressive (Grace, 2007).

The IAP2 Spectrum works well together with the Enabling Change framework to guide about the appropriate level of engagement. Enabling Change (Robinson, 2018) offers a useful matrix to understand when a certain level of engagement is adequate according to the level of complexity, and perceived sensitivity of the action. Straightforward actions of minimal sensitivity or risk may need little more than good information being provided to all stakeholders. However, proposals which are complex and require time and discussion to fully understand, and which also carry significant levels of perceived risk or sensitivity, need processes which offer more involvement to stakeholders.

Figure 19. Consultation matrix.

Source: Les Robinson, 2002.

4.4.2 The participation levels of the Demonstration actions

The citizen engagement strategy to deploy in the Valencia is based on the different levels of engagement entailed by the LH interventions according to the two models described above.

The interventions planned in Valencia were therefore analysed together with the technical partners in charge, and the level of participation selected according to the goals of the actions, their complexity and their sensitivity.

In order to understand the features and requirements of the actions, and to establish the level of participation entailed, data were collected from partners through an ad hoc questionnaire². The data collected were validated during the WP2 meetings.

INFORM

Citizen engagement goal: To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed.

² The G-Form questionnaire can be consulted [here](#).

Information only involves a one-way flow of information from the administration to citizens, nevertheless it is an important foundation for community engagement since it builds knowledge and allows citizens to understand the public decision-making process and to take informed decisions.

The Inform level is appropriate in situations where there is no opportunity for the public to influence decision-making and simply informing them is the appropriate activity. The inform level of public participation requires to give citizens what they need to fully understand the action and decision and to reach their own conclusions as to the appropriateness and adequacy of the decision.

Information is so important for the citizens' engagement, intended as the involvement in the decision making and policies processes, that some authors suggest even to consider that the Inform level should be placed across the Spectrum, demonstrating that effective engagement requires a strategic flow of information (Chappell, 2016). Indeed, all the relevant stakeholders (administration, business, academia, civil society) will be targeted at the Inform level about all the Lighthouse interventions in Valencia. Moreover, public demonstration sites will be used for exposition and training purposes, through open visits and seminars on site. They are listed in the **TABLE 3**:

	<p>ENERGY. A.9.Civic centre; A.11.Retrofitting of urban development local agency; A.13.Pilot Wave Energy Converter ; A.14.Sewerage energy recovery system; A.26.humble lampposts (10).</p>
	<p>MOBILITY. A.23.2multimodal hubs; A.25.Management of EV parking places.</p>
	<p>ICT. A.29.Smart District Energy Management System (SDEMS); A.32.IoT data integration with the VLCi smart city platform.</p>
	<p>CITIZENS. A.36.50/50 Programmes; A.41.District refurbishment local investment fund; A.46.Local toolkit for development of NZE Buildings; A.47.Local toolkit for RES production, storage, self-consumption; A.50.City Mentoring.</p>

Table 3 - Demonstration sites

 CONSULT

Citizen engagement goal: To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed, listen to and acknowledge concerns and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

The Consult level of public participation focuses on feedback and is the basic minimum opportunity for public input to a decision: the administration obtains feedback about plans, ideas, options or issues, but with little interaction.

The Consult level is appropriate when specific input is sought from citizens for the decision making, but early engagement is not possible throughout the process.

Several Lighthouse interventions in Valencia require the willingness of citizens to provide information, especially on their energy consumption and behaviour, and the energy performance of their houses, in order to improve the energy efficiency and reduce costs. The interventions are in fact part of a wider strategy of high-performance district, including the integration of RES into the buildings, as well as passive solutions (Energy), together with monitoring and control through ICT integration (ICT), and they require the awareness (information) and input from the public (consultation). Moreover, several of these actions require the installation of devices within residential buildings, and the access to them (TABLE 4); this level of participation, provided that the action was already defined and citizens were not involved in it (decision making), was thus considered as Consult level. This applies to the energy interventions A1-A6 and the related A28 under the ICT pillar. Mobility interventions A17-A19 and A22 also require input from neighbours in the district on needs and habits related the services offered by e-bikes (A17, A22) and access to residential buildings for the charging points (A18, A19).

	<p>ENERGY. A.1.Reconstruction of 16 houses; A.2. PVintegration 223kW; A.3.Electrical storage for self-consumption 1100 kWh model integr.; A.4.400 Smart meters; A.5.150 smart-controls; A.6.retrofitting of 548 private houses; A.12.Solar thermal integration.</p>
	<p>MOBILITY. A.17.5 e-bikes (2 for disabled mobility, 3 for last mile logistics); A.18.72 EV charging points; A.19.3 V2G pilots; A.22.Last mile logistics based on e-bikes.</p>
	<p>ICT. A.28.Smart Home Energy Management System (SHEMS).</p>

Table 4 - Actions to be performed which require the installation of devices

 INVOLVE

Citizen engagement goal: To work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.

Promise to the public: we will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

At the Involve level, citizens are invited into the process to a greater extent than with Consult: the goal is to work with the public throughout the process, it is a two-way exchange of information that encourages discussion and provides an opportunity to influence the outcome. The Involve level implies processes ensuring there is common understanding of the issue and that citizens views, concerns and aspirations are reflected in the development of options or approaches.

At the Involve level, the public is invited into the process, usually from the beginning, and is provided multiple if not ongoing opportunities for input as decision-making progresses. While the promise implies that issues raised should be taken into account, decisions at this level are generally made by the administration rather than the public.

The Involve level is appropriate when people have some investment in an issue, but it is not very controversial nor has major implications for other people.

COLLABORATE

Citizen engagement goal: To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.

Promise to the public: We will look to you for direct advice and innovation in formulating solutions and incorporate your advice and recommendations into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.

At the Collaborate level, the public is directly engaged in decision-making and it is involved in an interactive process with an emphasis on two-way processes. The Collaborate level of citizen engagement includes all the elements of Involve but takes it a step further. Collaborate often includes the explicit attempt to find consensus solutions. However, similar to the Involve level of participation, the administration is still the ultimate decision-maker. The degree to which consensus will be sought and how much decision authority the administration will be willing and able to share must be made explicit.

At this level it is important to create trust and to ensure that there is genuine engagement and this can be costly and time-consuming. Besides, there can be risks involved in processes at this level. If the promise is seen as being broken (e.g., if members of a community cannot agree of ways forward, or if some sections of the community feel their views were not taken into account), trust can be broken and future relationships with key stakeholders can be significantly damaged. Collaborate is particularly useful for controversial issues and complex problems because it entails a high level of participation.

Most of the non-technical interventions, dealing with innovative businesses, urban planning and citizens' engagement imply the participation of the public at some point and to some extent, including the participation in the decision making process in some cases (TABLE 5). These actions therefore can be placed across the Involve and Collaborate levels, which some authors define the Deliberate level, and the engagement activities should be defined accordingly.

	<p>CITIZENS. A.34.City policies update; A.35.Employment initiative; A.37.Social & local entrepreneurship program; A.38.Business opportunities; A.39.Shared PP investment models; A.40.Prosumer energy cooperatives; A.42.Upscaling plan; A.45.Citizen engagement; A.48.Local strategy to mitigate energy poverty.</p>
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Table 5 - Actions specifically focused on Citizens' Engagement

The level of participation of the interventions aimed at policy improvements is still to determine.

EMPOWER

Citizen engagement goal: To place final decision-making in the hand of the public.

Promise to the public: We will implement what you decide.

At the Empower level, the public has the opportunity to make decisions for themselves.

It does not necessarily mean it is the highest level of community engagement. Whereas Collaborate requires a high level of community engagement, Empower does not necessarily require the same degree of community engagement. At this level, a decision could be made by the community through a process that requires little interaction or engagement (e.g., a referendum). The most common activities at this level are public voting or ballot measures.

Governments rarely conduct public participation at the Empower level because of a perception that they are not permitted to delegate their decision-making authority to the public. However, the promise of the Empower level is not about statutory authority but a promise to *implement what you decide*. Responsibility for the decision can still lie with the elected body while honouring the promise (Susskind, 2008). Indeed, the MATchUP engagement approach is based on empowering citizens by giving some authority and power in the decision-making process.

Under the Citizen engagement intervention, citizens may be involved in prioritizing district needs and requirements through open participatory activities, and they could work on proposals through online consultations.

	<p>CITIZENS.</p> <p>A.45.Citizen engagement.</p>
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The level of participation of the Valencia Lighthouse interventions are summarized in the **FIGURE 20:**

LH Intervention					
	INFORM	DEMO	CONSULT	INV&COLL	EMPOWER
A.1	✓		✓		
A.2	✓		✓		
A.3	✓		✓		
A.4	✓		✓		
A.5	✓		✓		
A.6	✓		✓		
A.7	✓				
A.8	✓				
A.9	✓	✓			
A.10	✓				
A.11	✓	✓			
A.12	✓		✓		
A.13	✓	✓			
A.14	✓	✓			
A.26	✓	✓			
A.27	✓				
A.15	✓				
A.16	✓				
A.17	✓		✓		
A.18	✓		✓		
A.19	✓		✓		
A.20	✓				
A.21	✓				
A.22	✓		✓		
A.23	✓	✓			
A.24	✓				
A.25	✓	✓			

LH Intervention						
		INFORM	DEMO	CONSULT	INV&COLL	EMPOWER
A.28		✓		✓		
A.29		✓	✓			
A.30		✓				
A.31		✓				
A.32		✓	✓			
A.33		✓				
A.34		✓			✓	
A.35		✓			✓	
A.36		✓	✓			
A.37		✓			✓	
A.38		✓			✓	
A.39		✓			✓	
A.40		✓			✓	
A.41		✓	✓			
A.42		✓			✓	
A.43		✓				
A.44		✓				
A.45		✓			✓	✓
A.46		✓	✓			
A.47		✓	✓			
A.48		✓			✓	
A.49		✓				
A.50		✓	✓			
A.51		✓				
A.52		✓				

Figure 20. Level of public participation in LH interventions- Valencia

4.5 Definition of the MAtchUP virtual window [updated]

The following virtual channels and sites will be used for the MAtchUP citizen participation.

Web platforms

- MAtchUP website (<http://www.matchup-project.eu/>) - active
- **[UPDATED]** MAtchUP local website (<http://www.elmaritiminnova.eu/>) – **current status: active**
- #DecidimVLC – link to MAtchUP under construction

Social networks

Twitter (@matchupEU)

Other social networks at the project or local level will be studied and built, if relevant, by the Communication Local Desk, according to the Communication Strategy (see Chapter 6).

In particular, with reference to the websites, the partners in charge of the Communication Local Desk (LNV, VAL), the Engagement strategy (KVEL) and the Municipal Decentralization and Participation services are working together in order to identify synergies and connections. In particular, the virtual infrastructure envisaged for the engagement process under MAtchUP will be based on the main MAtchUP website, for the general dissemination of the project; the local MAtchUP website, with full and detailed information on the LH interventions; finally, the implementation of MAtchUP online participatory processes, such as proposals, forum, ballots, among others, hosted by the

current municipal website devoted to participation (#DecidimVLC). In particular, the local MatchUP website and #DecidimVLC will be connected, and the technical features are at the present date under development.

The planned structure is shown in **FIGURE 21**, **FIGURE 22** and **FIGURE 23**:

Figure 21. MAtchUP Virtual Infrastructure

#Decidim VLC, as mentioned above, is the virtual platform for the citizens' participation of the City of Valencia. The platform is based on the technology CONSUL, a tool developed by the City Council of Madrid in Open Source and adapted by the city Council of Valencia. #DecidimVLC is currently under a process of widening its features. Among others, the connection to ongoing projects entailing participatory actions is planned. Therefore, a connection to MatchUP and related participatory actions is planned and under analysis for development. The connection will be on one side addressed (1) to provide information on the project engagement activities and, on the other side, (2) to host MatchUP online participatory processes, where needed, in #DecidimVLC, as shown in the **FIGURE 22**.

Figure 22. MAtchUP Virtual Infrastructure (#DecidimVLC)

The MatchUP local website will host information on the LH interventions that will be implemented in Valencia, and detail on each action, including resources, events and associated participatory activities. The VLC Open Data will be visualized and/or hosted. As said, when needed, the MAtchUP local website will address the user to the participatory platform #DecidimVLC, as shown in the **FIGURE 23**.

The information will be available in Spanish and Valencian.

Figure 23. MAtchUP Virtual Infrastructure (local website)

4.6 Definition of the MAtchUP F2F infrastructure [updated]

The F2F infrastructure designed for the MAtchUP citizen engagement strategy is showed in **FIGURE 24**.

Figure 24. MAtchUP F2F infrastructure

MATchUP Meeting Point. This will be the site of the MATchUP participation activities. The aim is to provide information on the project and LH interventions and to host the participatory events, seminars, workshops and meetings. The MATchUP Meeting Point will be the point of reference and development of the Project and it will serve as:

- ❖ The working place of the Coordination and Management Group (CMG), in charge of the coordination and management of the citizen engagement strategy;
- ❖ The central office for the Communication and Dissemination of the activities developed. The Local Communication Desk may be located here;
- ❖ The meeting point and debate among the sectoral committees, technicians, the citizens, research institutions and the experts from the municipality;
- ❖ The site for the development of assemblies, workshops and meetings.

Current status (M24)

The "Marítim Innova" office was created, located at LAS NAVES. C/Joan Verdaguer, Nº16 – Valencia.

Weekly Meeting “Dijous MAtchUP”. As a permanent and visible space for meeting, the MAtchUP staff for the citizen engagement will be available to the public once per week (the so called “Dijous MAtchUP”/“MAtchUP Thursdays”). The weekly event Dijous MatchUP will be hosted on a rotating basis across the five neighbourhood of the district. The contents of the event will vary according to the status and needs of the LH interventions and the participatory process, and may include: driving group meetings; meetings between LH interventions technical partners and neighbours; meetings with other key actors linked to the interventions (EDUSI, PIP, ARRU, PACSA, Employment Pact Foundation, SERVEF, etc.); information and news on the implementation of the interventions; training.

Current status (M24)

Weekly meetings “Dijous MAtchUP” are being used for internal team work coordination of the staff responsible of citizen participation. This appointment is used to organize meetings with the Driving Group and interviews with key stakeholders; to organize the workshops and events; to deepen and to monitor the planned activities; to coordinate the communication and dissemination.

Coordination and management group

The Coordination and Management Group (CMG), is composed by facilitators and technical partners who will be responsible of the contents and methodology throughout the whole process. The CMG Group establishes, since the start of the strategy, agile and flexible governance systems that will allow good communication and coordination towards citizens, technicians, policy makers and stakeholders.

It coordinates the different bodies and groups created for the engagement process. It also acts as a mediation team maintaining fluid communication and a close and continuous collaboration with the social and economic agents, addressing the problems that may arise from the confluence of divergent interests.

Current status (M24)

The citizens' engagement strategy is discussed during the WP2 meetings in Valencia, as part of the monitoring of the demo site actions and general discussion. The meetings involve all the WP2 partners, and relevant stakeholders when needed.

During the meetings, all the partners participating in the activities that involve citizens' engagement are informed. Moreover, the type of participation entailed in each moment and for each action is discussed. The status of the participatory activities, the design of the Dissemination and Communication strategy, joint initiatives to involve citizens and to disseminate actions are discussed.

Driving Group

Composition: CITIZENS + COORDINATION & MANAGEMENT TEAM.

Objective: Dynamization, information, training, coordination of the working groups.

Frequency of the meetings: to be confirmed.

It is constituted by the citizens and volunteers; and the technical group of management and coordination. The Driving Group is active along the whole process, is composed by people really engaged and who take on responsibility part of the process. This group of people is at the same time source of information and the centre of the process. The Driving Group is flexible, and new members can be invited whenever specific issues and themes require it. The DG may support in the data collection on their referring environments, on existing networks and relationships. The DG is able to self-manage many of the actions and initiatives that arise from the process.

Current status (M24)

The Driving Group was built in January-February 2019, based on the outcome of the participatory workshop held in Valencia on December 2018. The group is composed by key stakeholders from the quadruple helix of social innovation: Social Services Department; Fundació Observatori Canvi Climàtic – FOCC; Local initiatives (Barris Inclusius); Local development and employment Agency (Valencia Activa); Valencia Polytechnic University (ICT department and Ideas Institute); Energy Office of València; NGOs (Caritas), social enterprise (AEIOLUZ), Project partners (K-VELOCE, Las Naves).

The DG met each 2 months approximately along 2019 (three meetings were held along January – July 2019). It is an open group where people and entities are incorporated, according to specific topics, interests, etc. The main objectives are to increase the SOCIAL IMPACT of the MAtchUP actions in the district and the city and to strengthen synergies with other existing and ongoing projects and initiatives. The DG organizes activities, seeks for mutual support in projects, shares resources and works in the detection of solutions and initiatives to face the needs and problems identified in the diagnosis. Until now, the DG has been working in several themes, such as open data, employment opportunities, energy poverty, social innovation, etc. (more details in [CHAPTER 5](#)).

Sectoral Committees

Composition: THEMATIC WORKING GROUPS + STAKEHOLDERS + CITIZENS.

Objective: proposals elaboration, debates, reflection, training.

Frequency of the meetings: self-managed with support where needed.

These commissions work in specific domains and they are composed by technicians, experts in the field. They are groups already working in the district (i.e. the identified WGs of the District Council), or under MAtchUP (such as the Thematic Working Groups managed under WP1) and/or created answering to specific needs and interests. Further Sectoral Commissions may be created around a specific MAtchUP performance, or depending on other needs or interests linked to the program. The Communication and Dissemination Group is also a specific sectorial committee, dedicated to ensuring a correct connection with the citizens of the field and the transparency of the process.

Current status (M24)

The Sectoral Committees emanate from the Driving Group. They have been generated to deal with different aspects or themes that are of interest to specific agents and that are relevant to the project, such as data, employment and entrepreneurship opportunities, young talent, education or links with initiatives such as the “challenges” of the Ideas Institute of the UPV.

These groups are still in a very initial state, and they will be developed as the project progresses.

Spaces of decision making

Composition: THEMATIC WORKING GROUPS + DRIVING GROUP + CITIZENS + STAKEHOLDERS.

Objective: decision making, prioritization.

Frequency of the meetings: 3-4 times/ year, when needed.

When working groups and sectoral committees make proposals that need an open space of decision for all the citizens, specific spaces of decision-making need to be set up. In these spaces, the proposals are legitimized and priority is given to the most urgent actions and proposals to work in the medium and long term.

Current status (M24)

A participatory workshop (WS3) was held in Valencia in December 2018 and it is fully described in [CHAPTER 5](#).

Monitoring Committee

Composition: DRIVING GROUP + CITIZENS + STAKEHOLDERS

Objective: monitoring, transparency, dialogue with public administration.

Frequency of the meetings: quarterly.

The monitoring committee is integrated by:

- ✓ Policy makers
- ✓ Process Promoters
- ✓ Representative associations
- ✓ Driving Group

This committee is informed during all the participative process. It is an essential part of the participatory process of defining the strategy, working as a supervisor of the negotiation in some pivotal moment and ensuring the transparency and the proper functioning of the citizens' involvement process. A fluid and continuous communication should be guaranteed between all the agents of the monitoring committee and in addition, control and information meetings are to be established.

The launch of the MAtchUP infrastructure was scheduled for December 2018 (M15), in occasion of the **City Needs and Priorities Workshop** (see the MAtchUP CE Strategies, p. 12 of this document, and D1.1, WP1).

Current status (M24)

The Monitoring Committee will begin once the implementation of the different actions progresses. It is expected in 2020.

5 Action Plan [updated]

5.1 City needs and priorities Workshop (WS3)

As mentioned above, under WP1, T1.1 City Advanced Characterization (related in D1.1) a participatory workshop was planned at M15, the **City needs and priorities workshop** (at city level).

This workshop was used as an open public event for the launch of the MAtchUP demonstration in Valencia and it was held in the district area. The workshop was aimed at identifying collaboratively the interest, opinions, and wishes from the public and at prioritizing the citizens' needs, in order to align the interventions to citizens' needs and priorities.

The results of the City needs and priorities workshop were aimed at further nurturing the planning of the Citizen Engagement activities.

5.2 City needs and priorities Workshop (WS3) outcome [new]

The workshop was held in Las Naves library in December 18th 2018.

During the meeting, participants worked at different levels and with different methodologies in the four areas: energy, mobility, ICT and actions addressed to citizens.

A total of 39 people attended the working session. The group represented the four helix of social innovation made up of Administration, Knowledge Transfer Centres, Companies, Citizenship and Civil Society Organizations.

WORKSHOP WS3	THEMATIC AREAS	ATTENDEEES
Local public administration	Energy, ICT, Urban planning, Citizens, Social inclusion, Employment and entrepreneurship	7
Public regional and supranational administration	Mobility	1
Academic sector	Mobility & ICT, Innovation	2
Private companies	Energy, Energy efficiency in buildings, ICT, Employment and entrepreneurship	4
Civil Society Organizations (CSOs)	Energy, Citizens, Social inclusion	5
Project partners	Energy, Mobility, ICT, Citizens	19
Participatory body	Citizens	1
		39

Table 6. WS3 Participants

The entities were selected keeping in mind the specificity of their working area, allowing them to contribute with a more global vision to the district and the city needs and priorities.

The workshop was divided in two parts. The first one dealt with the CITY DIAGNOSIS (*City needs and priorities Workshop*), while the second was focused on the DISTRICT (*District diagnosis Workshop*), delving into the project and its specific actions. The workshop agenda and conclusions are public and can be downloaded in Spanish [HERE](#).

❖ **CITY DIAGNOSIS**

The first working session of the day *WS3. City needs and priorities Workshop* is part of the wider Participatory Diagnosis planned under WP1, aimed at contributing to the creation of a demand side scenario, which identifies the city needs and priorities together with a detailed city performance diagnosis (see D1.4).

In line with the methodology drawn, the cities involved in MatchUP performed a Participatory Diagnosis through three different workshops, associated to these three-steps:

- Step 1: Analysis of city plans and city indicators (WS1)
- Step 2: City performance characterization (WS2)
- Step 3: City needs and priorities identification (WS3)

Accordingly, WS3 in Valencia was addressed to include in the city characterization the interests, opinions, and wishes from a broader stakeholder group, involving private companies and citizens as well. Needs and wishes were gathered within WS3 and prioritized through structured and appropriate methodologies.

The results of WS are described in detail in D1.4 (p. 51-60) and summarized below.

	CURRENT SITUATION	NEEDS AND PRIORITIES
ENERGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Low influence of energy modal split on GHG emissions ▪ Low level of RES ▪ High energy consumption ▪ Uninsulated buildings ▪ Fuel poverty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RES production increase ▪ Open data available on energy consumption ▪ Energy positive city by 2050 ▪ Prosumer cooperative in the Maritime District ▪ Innovative local start-up and energy cooperatives ▪ Energy efficiency in housing building stock by refurbishment ▪ Fuel poverty eradication

	CURRENT SITUATION	NEEDS AND PRIORITIES
MOBILITY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Different mobility behaviours depending on area: inner vs. metropolitan area. Targeted solutions are needed ▪ Inner area: good intermodality; good quality of public transport ▪ Metropolitan area: private vehicle with low occupancy; public transport to improve ▪ Public transport not competitive towards private vehicle; different service providers and ticketing ▪ Lack of charging points network in public spaces ▪ Cycling lanes increasing in number and length, and improving in connections ▪ Mobility paradigm recently changed into SUMP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Common vision on the metropolitan area, combining Urban planning, Environment and Mobility ▪ Change in mobility behaviour through targeted solutions ▪ Designing for people principle ▪ Competitive public transport and unified ticketing ▪ Infrastructures improvement ▪ Intermodal splits improvement ▪ Promotion of new solutions (carpooling, car sharing, mobility as a service, ...) ▪ Integrated solutions for health improvement
ICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Existing ICT vertical management systems to manage the municipal services and other urban infrastructures ▪ VLCi Platform develop as a Smart City platform, allowing to join and analyse data from ICT vertical management systems ▪ Free Wi-Fi access at public buildings, buses and public parks and gardens ▪ Added value provided by existing ICT services managed by private entities (Citizen safety, Citizen as a sensor, ...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Smarter services, offered proactively, ubiquitously and in a more integrated way ▪ Inclusiveness: Information Literacy (IL) and full inclusion ▪ City infrastructures empowerment (5G; energy savings) ▪ Personal data protection (data privacy by default) ▪ Standardized KPIs ▪ Citizen engagement ▪ Other services: technology coverage for citizen security and pest control; digital healthcare
CITIZENS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High levels of citizens' engagement, civic awareness and participation ▪ Lack of integration of certain groups ▪ Unequal access to public services (urban segregation and inherited vulnerability due to the place of residence) ▪ Gentrification ▪ Gender gap in health and employability ▪ Ageing population ▪ New productive model and new model of labour relations; unemployment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Access and quality of information ▪ Inclusiveness and accessibility: inclusive employment and education; inter-culturality promotion; universal accessibility paradigm across all local policies (housing, mobility, ...) ▪ Poverty reduction, incl. fuel poverty ▪ Ensuring access to decent housing ▪ Gender equality ▪ Services addressed to ageing population; promotion of silver economy ▪ Employment increase, focused specially on women and youngsters (active employment policies) ▪ Sustainability and SDGs ▪ Local development approach to public planning and policies

Table 7. WS3 - City diagnosis main results

❖ DISTRICT DIAGNOSIS

The second working session of the day WS3. *District diagnosis Workshop* was specifically focused on the MAtchUP project and actions and addressed to stakeholders of the quadruple helix related to the project pilot site, the district *Poblados Marítimos*.

The workshop was aimed to share and explore baseline and demand side scenarios through previous diagnosis performed in the area and to define participatively how to optimize the project actions according to the shared diagnosis.

To this end, the working session included:

- The presentation of the project actions and dissemination channels to identify and monitor them (local brand, local webpage)
- The presentation of the main needs in the *Poblados Marítimos* district
- A participatory activity aimed at identifying potential activities and priorities to complement and optimize the MAtchUP actions, towards the main needs shared, and in general the opinion of participants

The participatory work was focused on public policies improvements and citizen participation (incl. education and training, engagement, dissemination), ICT tools and the promotion of employment and entrepreneurship, as a trigger to enhance the impact of the project actions on the inhabitant's quality of life (FIGURE 25).

Figure 25. WS3 District diagnosis approach

The main questions tackled along the working session were:

- **Q1.** How the project actions may improve the quality of life of the district inhabitants?
- **Q2.** How public policies improvements and citizen participation, ICT tools and the promotion of employment and entrepreneurship may trigger the project impact?

The session was divided into two thematic working groups: ENERGY and MOBILITY. Participants rotated from one table to another in two consecutive rounds. The thematic scope and the specific planned actions were presented in each table.

The bundles of project actions related to the topics of public policies improvement and participation, ICT and the promotion of employment and entrepreneurship were also presented in both groups. The operations related to these thematic areas are transversal and open to discussion and collaboration. This is the reason why the participative dynamic was centred in the reflection and collection of ideas in these three fields of action, considered as a trigger to strengthen and widen the impact of the project on the citizens' quality of life.

According to the workshop results, the main fields of action to optimize the impact of the project are: (1) Public policies improvement and citizen engagement; (2) Education and training; (3) Employment and entrepreneurship. Within the highlighted fields, the following priorities were identified.

(1) PUBLIC POLICIES AND CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

Communication strategy. Several participants stressed the importance of communicating the project actions, in order to guarantee their success and to ensure the participation of the district inhabitants. The need of messages targeted to the different groups composing the social environment of the district was also stressed. It is important to take advantage of the district scale and to work together with entities and actors to achieve a bidirectional and fluid communication.

Decision making and collaboration. Inter-sectoral and inter-organizational collaborations are considered relevant to ensure the impact of the project actions on the district. Collaborations with district communities, neighbourhood entities, professional associations, or universities were mentioned as potential examples. Besides, participants claimed the opportunity of being engaged in the decision making of the actions, whenever possible, for instance to determine the location of the screens of the MULTIMODAL HUBS, the information they offer, or final use that the electric bicycles will have.

(2) EDUCATION AND TRAINING

Citizenship education / education in values. Participants stressed as a priority the promotion of citizenship education and education in values relying on existing community actors working to increase environmental and social awareness (energy efficiency, sustainable mobility...).

Vocational education and training. Participants highlighted the need of vocational education and training linked to mobility and energy, creating the possibility of new job opportunities in the district.

(3) EMPLOYMENT AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

New services and products. Innovative services and products related to the new technologies can enhance the district sense of belonging and the inhabitants' quality of life and therefore they could be promoted to strengthen the project impact in the district in the following fields:

- **Mobility:** support services addressed to users with special needs; promotion and use of local technology resources, and local trade as a flagship; telework or telecommuting as an opportunity to spend more time in the district.
- **Energy:** RES promotion; existing and ongoing prosumer cooperative project, seeking to promote the prosumer profile (people producing and consuming energy) and the possibility of creating a community to pay for the needed initial investment.

eVehicles supporting services and new business. Several ideas arose related to the acquisition and use of new electric vehicles (last mile services, attention to people with special needs, ...) and the maintenance of these new services.

Social incentives. Social incentives may be used to promote the sustainable mobility and energy efficiency, such as

- Public transport fare reduction
- Gamification and awards related to responsible energy consumption at home

(4) TRANSVERSAL ISSUES

Inclusiveness. Within both working groups, the inclusiveness arose as a transversal condition to ensure across any potential action and initiative, in terms of:

- Universal accessibility
- Care and inclusion of vulnerable age groups (elderly; children)
- Gender perspective
- Inclusion of vulnerable groups

Integrated approach. Participants stressed the interconnection among all the identified priorities and the three fields of action, as shown in the following **FIGURE 26**.

CONCLUSIONS WS3

Figure 26. WS3 District diagnosis main conclusions

5.4 Citizen Engagement activities [updated]

The first version of the Citizen Engagement Strategy (D2.12) included a preliminary list of activities suitable for each level of participation, summarized in **FIGURE 27**. The activities and tools to develop were then fine-tuned with the district citizens during the Workshop WS3 and their current status is detailed in the following sections.

Figure 27. Public participation toolkit.

Source: <http://tompkinscountyny.gov/tccp/publicparticipation>

Current Status (M24)

According to the analysis of the participation level inherent to the MAtchUP actions and the outputs of the participatory workshop WS, the efforts addressed to the citizen engagement have been focused on three main action lines:

- (1) Inform, including communication, dissemination and demonstrative actions
- (2) Consult
- (3) Collaborate

5.5 Inform [new]

The objective of the Inform participation level is to provide balanced and objective information in a timely manner. This participation level involves all the project actions, that will be thus properly presented and disseminated along their lifecycle. The activities are scheduled as follows.

	Y1		Y2		Y3		Y4		Y5	
	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2
Info	Kick Off		Public launch & WS3							
Local brand			Public launch website							
Demo										

Table 8. Informative Activities Schedule

5.5.1 Information on MAtchUP actions at the local level

Information is an important foundation for community engagement since it builds knowledge and allows citizens to understand the public decision-making process and to take informed decisions. Indeed, the WS3 results highlighted the importance of communicating the project actions, in order to guarantee their success and to ensure the participation of the district inhabitants.

Therefore, updated information about the MAtchUP actions and their status is provided to citizens and stakeholders through events and publications.

The following main events took place along M1-M24 in Valencia:

- Kick Off meeting, 12/2017 (M3). To inform all the stakeholders about MAtchUP Project the project was launched with the presence of the city Mayor.
- Participative workshop WS, 12/2018 (M15). The collaborative event included the description in-depth of the project actions through presentations and a dedicated actions booklet, available to participants.
- Public launch of the local brand and website, 03/2019 (M18). The event was organized with the aim of widely disseminating the project local brand and website *El Marítim Innova*.

The publications on the project actions are released on institutional websites and social media of the MAtchUP local partners, as part of the project communication strategy (Chapter 6, and WP8 related deliverables). Some examples are shown in [FIGURE 28](#).

Figure 28. MAtchUP social media

However, given the importance of this activity within the citizen engagement strategy, a local brand and a local website (public and open) were developed, where the actions are fully described in local languages and their status will be updated and shared with citizens along the project lifecycle.

5.5.2 Local brand and website “El Marítim Innova”

As mentioned, *the inform level of public participation requires to give citizens what they need to fully understand the action and decision and to reach their own conclusions as to the appropriateness and adequacy of the decision.* A local brand was thus developed, with the aim of increasing the identification between the area of action and its population with the project. It is important that citizens and the rest of involved actors in the Valencian innovation ecosystem understands the objective of the project and the actions implemented.

The local brand includes both, elements of the original image of the MAtchUP project and elements from the city maritime district context, under Innovation as a key word for both environments:

Figure 29. MAtchUP local brand - El Marítim Innova

With the same aim, a local Project website was developed, in order to increase the actions understanding, dissemination and impact. The MAtchUP local website is active,

named as EL MARÍTIM INNOVA (i. e. the district innovates). The local website has the following URL: <https://elmaritiminnova.com/>. It has been developed in the two official languages of the Valencian community: Valencian and Spanish.

This website, with a simple and direct language, was designed under a blog structure which makes it easy to navigate and consult.

It will evolve as the project progresses to make it increasingly more interactive. These adaptations will be applied as the implementation of the actions progresses.

Figure 30. MATCHUP local website - Heading

HOMEPAGE. Summary of all content. Slider with recent news

The main sections of the MATCHUP local website are:

- ABOUT
- ACTIONS
- PARTICIPATE
- VIEWER
- RESOURCES

ABOUT. Explanation of what the EL MARÍTIM INNOVA initiative, concretely, and the MATCHUP project, in general, are. In this section the user will find the link to the general page of the project <https://www.matchup-project.eu/>. Also, all the local partners' logos can be found.

Figure 31. MAtchUP local website - About

ACTIONS. The actions are divided into 4 groups: ENERGY, MOBILITY, ICT AND CITIZENSHIP. They are shown as a mosaic, with a small image and a title understandable by the general public.

Each action is explained with an entry, which includes an image and a brief description. It also indicates the state in which it is: START-IN PROCESS-FINISHED.

As we have already mentioned, in the future, the possibility of introducing more information in each of the entries is planned while the different actions are developed and implemented: videos, images, etc. as well as the connection with other platforms that introduce more participation and visualization functionalities.

Figure 32. MAtchUP local website - Description of the actions

PARTICIPATE. This section explains the different ways of getting informed and participating.

The contact details of the project are given and those interested are invited to visit the "El Marítim Innova" OFFICE, located in Las Naves / C/Joan Verdeguer, 16. Here there will be staff with information about the project and events and citizen engagement activities that are underway.

This section gives the option to the user to leave their contact details and the possibility of leaving comments about the project. The message arrives directly to the official mail created expressly for the project and managed by the staff of the LOCAL OFFICE, previously mentioned.

Other ways of communication are telephone, e-mail elmaritiminnova@lasnaves.com and the possibility to participate in the published activities in the News section.

As it was told in the introduction of this section, we pursue to include Consul features to our Matchup Project for those actions with the highest level of implication. The objective is to work closely with the responsible department in the municipality of Valencia to make the adaptation as soon as possible. In any case, the development of these new functionalities depends on the level of development of each MATCHUP action and the degree of citizen involvement necessary for each of them.

Figure 33. MATCHUP local website - Participatory tool

VIEWER. This page is under construction by one of the partners of the Project (UPV). UPV will host the viewer ("Dashboard") where the user would be able to view the generated open data and those from VLCi considered relevant for the project and for citizens who participate in it.

RESOURCES. This section is divided into:

- NEWS
- INNOBLOG
- GOOD PRACTICES

Figure 34. MAtchUP local website - Resources

- **NEWS.** The news derived from the project are shown as a mosaic. Official presentations, workshops, as well as news that report on issues related to the project that are useful for the citizen, such as calls for rehabilitation grants, subsidies to the energy efficiency improvement, etc. are allocated in this section.
- **INNOBLOG.** In this section, news about innovation in the areas covered by the project will be collected. The staff responsible for communication and citizen engagement will be responsible for collecting articles and news, with the collaboration of local partners and experts in different fields.
- **GOOD PRACTICES.** As a complement to the web and as part of the work done in the actions A.35, A.37 and A.38 a repository of good practices in the field of Smart Cities has been created. The selection criteria have been designed to collect initiatives in the areas of employment and entrepreneurship, social innovation and citizen participation, which can be adapted to the Valencian context and with the possibility of being replicated.

5.5.3 Visits to the demo sites

Several visits will be realized to the demo site, allowing citizens to fully understand the actions features and implications. Besides, the visits will enhance the demonstration objective of the project. The visits will start progressively, as soon as the actions deployment is finalized (M36) and will target representatives of the quadruple helix of open innovation: public administration and public services; private sector; citizens and civil society organizations; and research organizations and university. Besides, special attention will be paid to young people and the demonstration activities will tackle primary and secondary schools in the district. The public demonstration sites that will be used for exposition and training purposes, through open visits and seminars on site are listed in the [TABLE 9](#).

	<p>ENERGY. A.9.Civic centre; A.11.Retrofitting of urban development local agency; A.13.Pilot Wave Energy Converter ; A.14.Sewerage energy recovery system; A.26.humble lampposts (10).</p>
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	<p>MOBILITY. A.23.2multimodal hubs; A.25.Management of EV parking places.</p>
	<p>ICT. A.29.Smart District Energy Management System (SDEMS); A.32.IoT data integration with the VLCi smart city platform.</p>
	<p>CITIZENS. A.36.50/50 Programmes; A.41.District refurbishment local investment fund; A.46.Local toolkit for development of NZE Buildings; A.47.Local toolkit for RES production, storage, self-consumption; A.50.City Mentoring.</p>

Table 9. Demonstration sites

5.4 Consult [new]

The objective of the Consult participation level is to obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.

ENERGY & ICT. Actions towards energy consumption and behaviour, and the energy performance in private houses require the willingness of citizens to provide information and they are therefore tackled under this level of participation, in the field of energy and ICT.

	<p>ENERGY. A.1.Reconstruction of 16 houses; A.2. PV integration 223kW; A.3.Electrical storage for self-consumption 1100 kWh model integr.; A.4.400 Smart meters; A.5.150 smart-controls; A.6.retrofitting of 548 private houses; A.12.Solar thermal integration.</p>
	<p>ICT. A.28.Smart Home Energy Management System (SHEMS).</p>

Table 10. Actions entailing consultative level of participation – ENERGY & ICT

An innovative set of smart meters and controllers will be deployed in 548 dwellings located in the *Poblados Marítimos* district and associated with actions A.4, A.5, A.6 and A.28, with the objective of gathering energy performance data to feed A.28 SEHMS. To this end, potential users need to be identified and recruited, and a communication campaign deployed accordingly, as shown in the following schedule.

	Y1		Y2		Y3		Y4		Y5	
	S1	S2								
Potential users' identification										
Communication campaign										
Recruitment										
Education campaign										

Figure 35. Consultative Activities Schedule – ENERGY

The citizen engagement bodies and tools supported the identification and engagement of potential users. In a first place, potential dwellings have been targeted, thanks to the cooperation of the Plan Cabanyal, in charge of managing the municipal aids for the retrofitting of private houses in the district. The communication campaign was designed (leaflet in **FIGURE 36**) and it will target also the general public in the district, with the aim of widening the campaign results.

Figure 36. Communication campaign leaflet (A.4, A.5)

LNv dedicated staff will be trained to offer desk assistance to users and KVEL and LNv will then support the partners in charge of the devices (WITRAC and ETRA) along the recruitment phase.

The engaged users will be trained on the use of the metering and controlling systems and on its support in reducing energy costs and consumption, strengthening the awareness on energy efficiency and metering measures.

Besides, education campaigns to the district inhabitants, not engaged directly, will be done to increase transparency, public acceptance of the remote control of the energy system, and awareness for energy saving potentials, ideally triggering further energy savings. The citizen engagement environment will support partners in charge of the education campaigns.

MOBILITY. Mobility interventions A17-A19 and A22 also require input from neighbours in the district on needs and habits related the services offered by ebikes (A17, A22) and access to residential buildings for the charging points (A18, A19), although specific consultative actions were not needed so far.

	<p>MOBILITY.</p> <p>A.17.5 e-bikes (2 for disabled mobility, 3 for last mile logistics); A.18.72 EV charging points; A.19.3 V2G pilots; A.22.Last mile logistics based on e-bikes.</p>
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Table 11. Actions entailing consultative level of participation - MOBILITY

5.6 Collaborate [new]

The objective of the Collaborate participation level is to partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making. This participation level covers the following non-technical actions dealing with public policies, citizens' engagement and innovative businesses, implying the participation of the public at some point and to some extent, including the participation in the decision-making process in some cases.

	<p>CITIZENS.</p> <p>A.34.City policies update; A.35.Employment initiative; A.37.Social & local entrepreneurship program; A.38.Business opportunities; A.39.Shared PP investment models; A.40.Prosumer energy cooperatives; A.42.Upscaling plan; A.45.Citizen engagement; A.48.Local strategy to mitigate energy poverty.</p>
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Table 12. Actions entailing collaborative level of participation

Accordingly, non-technical actions related to public policies improvement and participation, and the promotion of employment and entrepreneurship were discussed along the participative workshop WS3 in the first place, in order to build the priorities and action line of the collaborative space. The actions were approached as a trigger to strengthen and widen the impact of the project on the citizens' quality of life.

Based on the WS experience and through a snow-ball methodology, the Driving Group was set up (See [DEFINITION OF THE MATCHUP F2F INFRASTRUCTURE \[UPDATED\]](#)), with the aim of building an action plan and working on the arisen priorities.

The following action lines were scheduled, based on WS3 and the Driving Group work.

	Y1		Y2		Y3		Y4		Y5	
	S1	S2								
Public policies										
Citizen engagement										
Education and training										
Employment & entrepreneurship										

Table 13. Collaborative Activities Schedule

5.6.1 Public policies

Public-private investments to mitigate energy poverty. Under non-technical action *A.39 Shared private-public investment models for sustainable energy consumption and circular economy*, several impact investment funds were analysed as potential models of private-public investment for sustainable energy consumption, and the Social Impact Bonds (SIB) financial scheme was identified as particularly relevant and innovative. The possibility of applying such a financial scheme in a real scenario under MATCHUP was explored. In particular, the action *A.48: Local strategy of Social Services and Local*

Energy Office to mitigate energy poverty at the district scale was identified as a priority for its potential wide impact on vulnerable groups and its social strong relevance in terms of beneficiaries and their quality of life. Organizations active in the field of energy poverty were consulted within and outside the Driving Group and expressed their general interest:

- Within DG: CARITAS, Social Services, Las Naves, Fundaci3n Observatori Canvi Climàtic - FOCC
- Outside DG: network "Red Conecta Energía"

The action A.48 will be thus closely monitored, and a pre-feasibility study performed on a sample of 200 households in the city. The pre-feasibility study will allow to identify principal stakeholders, inputs, outputs, outcome, impact. The results of the pre-feasibility study will be available as a case study and used to raise awareness about this innovative private-public investment model among local authorities, and to train their staff on it. The analysis will be based on the close cooperation established between KVEL, LNV, FOCC, Social Services and the Local Energy Office, in charge of A.48 action.

5.6.2 Citizen engagement

Decision making and collaboration. Inter-sectoral and inter-organizational collaborations are considered relevant to ensure the impact of the project actions on the district. To this end, during M1-M24 several bilateral meetings were held, in order to create synergies and joint initiatives with organizations active in the district interested in collaborating with the project. Key organizations were identified as part of the Ecosystem analysis, performed in D2.12.

Public Administration
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralization and participation service / <i>Serv. Participaci3n</i> - Employment and Entrepreneurship Department / <i>Serv. Empleo y Emprendimiento</i> - Housing Department / <i>Serv. Vivienda</i> - Social Welfare and integration Department / <i>Serv. Bienestar social e Integraci3n</i> - Plan Cabanyal Office - (IVE) Valencian Institute of Building / <i>Instituto Valenciano de la Edificaci3n</i> - Employment Pact Foundation / <i>Fundaci3n CV Pacto por el Empleo</i> - Inclusive Neighbourhoods Project / <i>Proyecto Barris Inclusius</i>
Private sector
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AEIOLUZ
Citizens and CSOs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CivicWise
Research and University
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Universidad Polit3cnica de Valencia, Instituto IDEAS - Universidad Polit3cnica de Valencia, UPV-ITEAM

Table 14. Stakeholders involved M1-M24

Open Data Sectoral Committee. One of the main fields of interest of participants is related with the availability of compatible and public data from different areas and bodies of the public administration, and citizen data. Some bottlenecks were identified, such as the existence of different platforms with non-standardized data and at different territorial levels; and the availability of data at different levels of aggregation. Given the interest in the field, open data will be one of the action lines within the Driving Group, and relevant stakeholders will be involved in training and thematic working sessions (MATCHUP project partner UPV- Universidad Politécnica de Valencia; representatives of the international network CIVIC WISE; representatives of the Statistical Office of the Valencia municipality).

5.6.3 Employment and entrepreneurship

Within the project, specific actions towards the identification and promotion of employment, entrepreneurship and business opportunities related with the Smart City process were planned (A.35, A.37, A.38). The need of focusing on employment and entrepreneurship actions arose also during the participative workshop WS3 and these actions have been thus prioritized and enhanced under the citizen engagement action, relying on existing plans and relevant stakeholders in the field. The Driving Group, built within the citizen engagement environment, has the role of enhancing efforts and multiplying effects to this end and it includes therefore actors active in the field of employment, entrepreneurship and the protection of vulnerable groups, such as:

- Employment Pact Foundation / *Fundación Pacto por el Empleo*
- Social Welfare and integration Department / *Serv. Bienestar social e Integración*
- LAS NAVES
- NGO CARITAS
- Polytechnic University of Valencia / *Universitat Politècnica de València*

The actions, aimed at exploring employment, entrepreneurship and business opportunities potentially triggered by the project, have been therefore approached in a coordinated and holistic way, relying on the same cooperation and participative channels built under the citizen engagement strategy (A.45) and analytical tools.

The three connected actions thus include:

- The **participatory diagnosis** on needs in the district and the involvement of the quadruple helix of the social innovation (citizens, public administration, academia, business), including the collaboration with relevant actors in the field. The diagnosis, realized on December 2018 (WS3), included both perspectives, in terms of employment and social and local entrepreneurship and business opportunities.
- The development of a **repository** on existing local, national and international initiatives related to employment, entrepreneurship and social innovation in smart city processes.

The repository is participative (members of the Driving Group are invited to feed it), public (hosted by the local website.³) and will last during the whole project lifecycle.

- The identification of job profiles, entrepreneurship opportunities, and the related **training and education needs** related to the technical actions through the collaborative work with the technical partners.

- **Dissemination** on employment, entrepreneurship and business opportunities within smart city processes. Several training and dissemination activities will be organized and one conference per year will be held on related themes, such as: employment and the energy transition, circular economy, social innovation. Synergies with existing initiatives and organizations will be actively pursued.

5.7 Monitoring

It would be desirable to establish monitoring devices throughout the MATCHUP project implementation process. These devices must contain criteria and indicators not just technical or quantitative, but also incorporate others defined in a more qualitative and participatory way.

The propose of both indicators' batteries (technical and citizens) is to be able to rectify and adapt the actions to the context and the specific time in which they must be developed, taking advantage of the opportunities (overflows) that appear during the implementation. This non-stop evaluation will allow us to certain conditions that do not coincide or were not considered in the initial situation during the performance of the actions.

It would be important to operationalize the monitoring process so that it can document, systematize, communicate and disseminate the information and learn about it.

In this sense it will be important to monitor not only the progress and results that the implementation of the actions will produce but as well, we would have to monitor the participation itself, with its own criteria and indicators. Again, these indicators will have to be both quantity and quality. It is important not to forget the cultural criteria that will indicate if we are reaching all sectors of the population of the district or there are population groups that are being excluded.

As tools for this monitoring we can use:

- Schedules
- Cohereniometers
- "Targets" tracking
- "Rubrics" tracking
- Monitoring tracking

³ <https://elmaritiminnova.com/category/buenas-practicas/>

5.8 Evaluation

The evaluation of the implementation process of MAtchUP will be one of the points in which it will be necessary to pay special attention. It would be advisable to introduce in addition to the technical evaluation, which aims to meet objectives set by the project, a more participatory evaluation that involves citizens and allows us to collectively analyse the results and the impact it is having on the population.

In this sense, and as we indicated in the previous section, it is important to differentiate between two types of evaluations that must occur simultaneously. On the one hand, the evaluation of the participatory process itself, and on the other, the evaluation of the impacts at the local level.

The indicators that are established for the evaluation must address the objectives in the short, medium and long term. These indicators can cover areas such as: type of agent involved and their degree of involvement, degree of self-management of the devices and established participation groups (motor group, work groups...), degree of legitimacy perceived in the decision spaces, etc)

As tools for the monitoring we can use:

- Evaluation "targets"
- Evaluation "rubrics"
- Indicators of evaluation of participation
- Impact assessment indicators.

5.9 Gantt Diagram

Figure 37. Gantt Diagram

6 Dissemination and Communication

Dissemination and Communication activities related to citizen engagement have started in September 2018. However, from the very beginning of the project, the city of Valencia has made a special effort to spread the project, focusing on its objectives and on the areas on innovation.

Therefore, we have invested a lot on social and online dissemination during every event and city where the project has been introduced, both in Valencia and in other cities. Furthermore, current D&C materials, like the flyer, the newsletter and the video, have been widely disseminated.

The most important contents of the actions have been sent to the local and national media to publish them. In order to reach and engage citizens, we have opted for a clear and simple communication with the aim to get catchy messages to engage citizens and local authorities.

Once explained to citizens the general aim of the project, we will proceed to segment the actions according to the degree of citizen involvement and the type of public. For this, we are currently evaluating several ways to engage the public, from dedicated and programmed marketing campaigns to informative actions dedicated to the whole city of Valencia.

6.1 Approach

Communication covers a wide range of actions targeted to several stakeholders or target audiences, and should also communicate evidence-based information about areas and contents directly related with the project, being those produced by the consortium or by third-parties. The most important objective (primary objective) is to engage citizens; secondarily, it is intended to engage and involve several stakeholders: research community, public administration, companies or investors, among others, to be detailed in the section 6.3.3 and in the table specifying the communication campaigns to be carried out in Valencia in the section 6.4. A Responsible Innovation Communication must select, curate and disseminate contents based on validated information but making easily affordable for all.

The communication activity within MAtchUP in Valencia will allow to collect data and distribute information, even from third parties, in order to optimise the engagement rate of all target groups potentially reached, including citizenship, investors, public administration officers and any other group susceptible to be considered as a multiplier entity (eg., civil society entities, NGOs, associations, foundations, cultural centres, libraries, etc.).

6.2 Local Communication Desk

In order to sustain the communication activity in Valencia, the Valencian Local Communication Desk was established, including personnel from VAL, LNV and KVEL.

The following table identifies the main organizational aspects of the Valencian Local Communication Desk are described: composition (team members and their role); relation with other institutional bodies; relation with MAtchUP partners and WPs.

Team members and their role	M ^a José Perales, Communication Officer (LNV) Barbara Branchini, Project Manager (KVEL) Fran Azorín, Citizen Engagement Expert (KVEL) Beatriz Vallina, Communication Officer (KVEL)
Relation with other institutional bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Agència Valenciana de la Innovació - AVI ▪ Asociación Valenciana Empresas Sector Energía - AVAESEN ▪ CLIMATE KIC Valencia ▪ Centro Europeo de Empresas e Innovación de Valencia - CEEI Valencia ▪ Fundación Ecología y Desarrollo - ECODES ▪ Ciudad Politécnica de la Innovación - CPI-UPV ▪ Red de Institutos Tecnológicos de la Comunidad Valenciana - REDIT ▪ Instituto Tecnológico de la Construcción - AIDICO ▪ Cluster de Energía de la Comunidad Valenciana ▪ Mesa de la Movilidad de Valencia ▪ Asociación Valenciana del Vehículo Eléctrico - AVVE
Relation with MAtchUP partners and WPs	ICE (WP8) WP2 partners (WP2) Fundación Cambio Climático

The Local Communication Desk is in charge of the local D&C strategy definition, including, identification of appropriate channels, messages and specific social media and communication formats to foster engagement.

6.3 Communication Strategy

In-line with the approach above, the communication strategy should be considered as:

- **Plan:** an intended course of action and a set of guidelines and actions for strategically approaching the citizens engagement.
- **Perspective:** a macro view of the strategy that involves planning, plotting, patterning, and positioning but after defining the outcome, that is engagement.

Engagement is a term widely used in the literature; **in order to differentiate the term as used in the Action Plan and in the literature about communication itself**, it must be clarified that “engagement” in Communication refers to the community and aims at reaching a long-term alliance and loyalty with a certain audience (Holt and Chambers 2017). Engagement is not restricted to the interaction, the participation in the pilot phase, or the involvement during a predefined period, while these could be considered as dimensions or outputs: engagement means a medium and long-term sustainable relationship with feasible changes at the behavioural level. In addition, the engagement of audiences contributes to sustainability of MAtchUP at medium and long-term (Hanson, Salmoni, and Volpe 2009).

How to engage targets seems to be the most difficult question to answer in this sense; this strategy considers that a multi-channel approach merging traditional and innovative media could contribute to accomplish the objective as expressed in the project proposal. Therefore, among others, Valencian partners will attend and organise special events,

use their networks and personal influence through interpersonal and direct communication, social media and also traditional press and mass media (at local level, in-line with the project scope). Actions planned are furtherly detailed in Section 5.2. Consequently, the communication strategy should consider:

- opposition research
- specific audience targeting
- constant adjustment of the messages, when needed and observed through
- continuous follow-up and tracking of actions and response.

In addition, attention must be paid to key message, the mean for message delivering, audience's reactions, if observable, and unintended results. For online communication, "engagement" will be measured as the rate resulting from impressions⁴ and actions⁵.

6.3.1 Situation Analysis

Before designing a communication strategy, current means, communities and resources available should be clarified. In the case of Valencia, the current media that could be used and optimised are:

- Policy learning platforms
- Website
- Social Media
- Newsletter
- Press and News Releases
- Events and conferences

During the formative phase and the iterative cycles for evaluating the communication strategy and campaigns performance, qualitative and quantitative data should be collected:

- Concepts, definition, characteristics, interests, symbols and language should be qualitatively analysed during the whole project to improve the communication campaigns' design and results
- Figures, rates and any other quantitative information could be collected in order to numerically evaluate the performance of the communication strategy and its campaigns.

⁴ An impression is when a publication (then, ads, articles, links, pictures, etc.) is fetched from its source, and is countable, regardless people performs an action or not. It could be defined as "times seen"

⁵ An action is when an individual performs some activity over a material or publication: e.g., read a flyer or a poster, like the content on Social Media, open an article on a website, etc.

6.3.2 Goal/objectives

A clear analysis of the situation leads to specifying the overarching goal and objectives that should be addressed by the campaign. Goals are broad targets. Objectives are more specific.

In sum, the goal is to recruit and engage the Valencian citizenship, as it is furtherly developed in [Section 2](#).

- increasing the impact of the CE (Citizenship Engagement) strategy (see Section 5)
- engaging them in other activities of the project
- communicate the project outcomes
- and assure the long-term sustainability of the project by demonstrating its current success among service-users.

6.3.3 Target audience

CE and Communication campaigns, even when they appear to address the general public, actually are directed toward specific and particular segments of the population as seen in [FIGURE 32](#). Some campaigns often include more than one target audience and can include both upstream and downstream groups.

Figure 38 - Target groups in-line with the 4 helixes for community engagement

These groups are furtherly explained in section 1 and the segmentation as regards the communication strategy for sustaining the Citizens' Engagement is drafter in section 6.4. The MATchUP strategy for Valencia includes both types of actions within the campaigns and the overall concept, upstream and downstream as defined in 6.3.4.

6.3.4 Strategy

Our strategy provides the linkage between the how and why components and a roadmap and sense of direction for generating the essential messages while also offering a rationale for the various actions that are proposed. The proposed strategy is based on communication campaigns, as defined below.

As regards the general approach but also the approach taken for implementing specific campaigns and actions, we can distinguish between upstream and downstream perspective.

- Upstream: instead of directly targeting the service-users, sometimes it would be better to reach a group that have interpersonal influence and can create change thanks to its relation with the service-users. In addition, these groups could be more likely to influence and have the ability to modify contextual factors. For instance, policy makers, public administration officers, community leaders or investors are groups to be considered in upstream actions. **However, upstream initiatives might be necessary for downstream efforts to be effective.**
- Downstream: recruiting service-users for the MAtchUP project will involve a significant effort in social marketing and public communication. The efforts should be made to design and implement the campaigns responding to the specific needs and preferences of citizens and main sub-targets.

6.3.5 Tactics

Strategies refer to broad roads on the map, and tactics are the small alleys or specific activities that must be undertaken to address the objectives of the campaign. In this case, personal networks of Valencian partners will be used for engaging the community and foster local awareness provides opportunities for unpaid media placement and contact with opinion leaders.

6.3.6 Media

MAtchUP's communication campaigns require the use of the aforementioned virtual platforms, mass media, interpersonal channels, small group meetings, and one-on-one discussions, as the case requires. Media of choice will depend on the key message and specific audience of each communication campaign.

6.3.7 Calendar

Each communication campaign should specify a calendar. The calendar must consider the following phases:

- **Launch** phase where the campaign is being initiated. It is common for the launch to involve the greatest media presence.
- The second phase is often the **body** of the campaign. Media are often used incrementally to remind the audience of the message.
- The third phase is usually the **final media push** before the campaign ends.

6.3.8 Summary of resources

The **TABLE 15** summarises the resources available for supporting the Citizen Engagement strategy (5.1.) through the aforementioned communication strategy. These resources will be considered for designing the communication campaigns plan, as developed in the section 6.4. Resources are grouped into groups of actions, specifying

degrees of participation, targets, tools and channels. The timing estimation is also considered for organising the overall plan for launching communication campaigns.

Table 15. Specification of available resources

Action / group of actions (if applicable)	Action degree of participation (see chapter 4.2)	Targeted public	C&D Tools	C&D Channels	Timing estimation
Necessary citizen participation (9 actions)	Involve and Collaborate	-Public authorities -Research Community -Policy Makers -Construction -Media -Investors -Citizens	- Communication campaign (Ref. Communication campaigns)- Short presentation video and interviews -Newsletter -Flyers -Webinars	-Policy learning platforms -Website -Social Media -Press and News Releases -Events and conferences	In order to correctly involve everyone, communication actions must begin at least three months before. To maintain people's attention, it is recommended that the communication campaign continue until the actions end.
Required involvement and recruitment of participants (4 actions)	Involve and Collaborate	- Citizens - Construction - Investors - Media	- Communication campaign (Ref. Communication campaigns)	- Mupis - Buses - Mailings - Press -Neighbourhood associations -Seminars/ workshops -Network "Conecta Energía	Actions Will be planned for starting 1 month before the A2-A5 and finishing 1 month after.
Necessary citizen involvement (12 actions)	Consult	-Research Community -Media -Investors -Citizens	-Short presentation video and interviews -Flyers	-Website -Press release -Social Media	You can start communicating one month before the action starts.
Demonstrative Actions (14 actions)	Inform	-Citizens -Research Community		-Website -Press release -Social Media	Communicating the action a couple of days before is enough.
A.45. Citizens' engagement	Empower	- Citizens - Business - Administration & - Research & Education	-Communication campaign (Ref. Communication campaigns)	-Policy learning platforms -Website -Social Media -Newsletter -Press and News Releases -Events	

6.4 Communication campaigns

The timing for executing the communication strategy will be organised in-line with the five communication campaigns specified above (see: Summary of resources).

Communication Campaigns (CC) comprise the overall organisation of the communication strategy and are in-line with the action plan (See Action Plan). These campaigns are ordered by lower to higher degree of use of resources and media effort. The figure below explains the general framework of the communication campaigns plan as well as the interaction with the Action Plan.

Figure 39 - Structure of the communication campaigns plan in-line with the action plan (section 5)

While [FIGURE 39](#) explains the overall structure, [TABLE 16. COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGNS PLAN](#) summarises the plan and organisation of communication campaigns, including targets, key messages, strategic approach, channels and resources.

Table 16. Communication campaigns plan

ID	Aim	Target group	Key Message	Approach	Channels	Resources
INFORM						
CC1.1.	To inform all stakeholders about the MAtchUP Project	Society as a whole	<i>MAtchUP proposes innovations in the fields of ICT, energy, sustainable entrepreneurship, mobility and transport and participation for all.</i>	Downstream	Local press/TV/Radio Social Media Virtual platform and local Website	Current media presence. Flyers Posters Personal networks and relations with media
CC1.2.	To disseminate the MAtchUP concept and aims		<i>That's how MAtchUP works We'll keep you up-to-date!</i>	Downstream	Website Social Media Local press, TV or radio	Current media presence.
CONSULT						
CC2.1	To obtain valuable and information feedback.	Citizens, service users	<i>Without you, MAtchUP does not make sense. Let us know your opinion!</i>	Downstream	Virtual platform and local Website Social Media Local press, TV or radio	Current media presence. New tools for feedback gathering (ref. 5.2. Citizen Engagement activities)
CC2.2.		Research community	<i>MAtchUP provides transferable information on how feedback could be obtained and analysed during the implementation of a large pilot project</i>	Upstream	Personal relations with universities and departments. Events and conferences	Current media presence.
INVOLVE						
CC3.1	To recruit citizens for participating in the pilot phase, expecting a high degree of involvement and collaboration .	Citizens Service-users	<i>Your participation led to economic development and prosperity for your neighbourhood and community. Participate in our events [substitute by the name of the event in each case] Join our online forum!</i>	Downstream	Events Local press/TV/Radio Social Media Virtual platform and local Website	Current media presence. Flyers Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media
CC3.2.		Public authorities Policy makers	<i>Sustainable entrepreneurship is a key for success. Participate in our events [substitute by the name of the event in each case] Join our online forum!</i>	Upstream	Virtual platform and local Website	media

CC3.3		Building Investors	<i>CE implies a higher value of products and business through validation and acceptance testing. Join our online forum!</i>		Virtual platform and local Website Social Media Newsletter Press and News Releases Events	
CC.3.4		Research community	<i>Community-engaged projects could contribute to fill the gap in implementation research. Join our online forum!</i>		conferences	
COLLABORATE						
CC4	To involve citizens in the decision-making process through the collaboration and consultation with the public in all relevant areas	Citizens Business Administration Research & Education	<i>We need your participation in the decision-making. We want to hear your voice: Join now the decision making process!</i> Strengthening collaboration for involving you in the decision-making process!	Downstream	Events Local press/TV/Radio Social Media Virtual platform and local Website	Current media presence. Flyers Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media
EMPOWER						
CC5	To raise loyalty and engagement during the pilot implementation	Service-users (i.e., people participating and already involved)	<i>Through MAtchUP, we implement what you decide. Digital democracy: what is it? MAtchUP project is focused on your needs. We focus on you.</i>	Downstream	Website Social Media Local press, TV or radio Virtual platform and local Website	Current media presence. Flyers Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media

6.5 Communication activities deployed M12-M24 [new]

According to the strategy and communication campaigns described above, different activities have been carried out in the MAtchUP project:

6.5.1 Kick Off and participatory workshops

Kick-Off To inform all the stakeholders about MAtchUP Project; the project was launched with the presence of the mayors of the three lighthouse cities: Valencia, Antalya and Dresden, at Las Naves innovation center, Valencia (Spain) in November 2017.

Participatory Workshops. During 2018, in occasion of three days of participatory workshops (see 6.5.3) were also organized with professionals from the energy, mobility, ICT and social sectors, as well as with residents of the *Poblats Marítims* district, in order to present the MAtchUP project, and disseminate its concept and aims.

In the first two sessions about 40 professionals from the energy, mobility, ICT and social sectors met in Las Naves to participate in the diagnostic phase of the city and thus study the possibilities of scaling the solutions designed within the project.

In the last one, different working tables were organized that revolved around the areas of action that the project addresses in the *Poblats Marítims* neighbourhood. The assistants worked on the diagnostic part of the city, on the real needs and provided their suggestions to improve the implementation of the actions in the different neighbourhoods in which the pilot will be developed. They also learned about the initiatives planned to promote citizen participation within the European MAtchUP project.

All these workshops were made public through press releases and social media publications. In addition, it entailed publication in different mass media.

6.5.2 Design and presentation of the local brand “El Marítim Innova”

To recruit citizens for participating in the pilot phase, expecting a high degree of involvement and collaboration the brand “*El Marítim Innova*” was created (see [CHAPTER 5.5.2. LOCAL BRAND AND WEBSITE “EL MARÍTIM INNOVA”](#)).

From October 2018 to March 2019, the creation of a local brand that was more understandable and close to the public was carried out, a website was designed to inform the status of the project and the image and the web were presented to the citizens and different stakeholders.

The first step was the creation of a local brand that could involve citizens, bring them closer to the project and make them not see it as a project outside their neighbourhood, and encourage them to participate when the time comes to recruit users to the pilot phase of the MAtchUP project. For this reason, the “*El Marítim Innova*” brand was created, which refers to the maritime district where the project is going to be implemented and the innovation to be carried out.

Together with the “*El Marítim Innova*” brand, a website (elmaritiminnova.com) was subsequently created and designed in which the different energy, mobility, ICT and citizen actions that will be produced in the project are explained, as well as informs of

the different activities that are being carried out (General Assembly, conclusions of the collaborative workshops, tender for the installation of vehicle charging points, etc.).

Subsequently, the brand was presented both to the different stakeholders and to the citizens, whose neighbourhood will be transformed thanks to the MAtchUP project.

The presentation of the brand involved the writing of press releases, publication in social networks, and appearance in different mass media. The objective of the public presentation was to present publicly and explain to the district the residents of the district what content it has and how the new local website of the MAtchUP project works.

Further information:

Pictures: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/inndeavalencia/albums/72157704235958112>

Video: <https://www.facebook.com/LasNavesINN/videos/446987395841684/>

6.5.3 Public events related to climate change

In 2018 and 2019 the MAtchUP project participated in events related to climate change. For the presentation of all these events, a press release was written, publications made on social networks and covered by different mass media.

2018 – “LA PLAÇA CANVIA PEL CLIMA. Within the initiative called *Valencia changes by the weather*, “LA PLAÇA CANVIA PEL CLIMA” was organized as a specific exhibition that took place in the Plaza of the City Council of Valencia. The MAtchUP project was announced to the citizens of Valencia during the exhibition.

Figure 40. LA PLAÇA CANVIA PEL CLIMA Leaflet

2018 – “ELS BARRIS CANVIEN PEL CLIMA”. Within the initiative called *Valencia changes by the weather*, “ELS BARRIS CANVIEN PEL CLIMA” was organized by the Valencia Climate and Energy Foundation, the City Council of Valencia, Las Naves and the Federation of Neighbourhood Association of Valencia as a presentation of ongoing relevant projects under development in the city. It was an open event addressed to all the people who were interested in innovative projects related to climate change.

Figure 41. ELS BARRIS CANVIEN PEL CLIMA Leaflet

The objective was to present the specific initiatives that are being developed in the city to fight against the climate change. Together with the Matchup project, the following initiatives were presented and discussed with the attendants:

- "Presentation of the heat map of the city of Valencia". Alejandro Carbonell, Green Urban Data.
- "Innovative plastic management in Sant Marcel·lí". Javier Ibáñez, Las Naves (Plastic Circle Project).
- "Improvement in the response of emergency services to climate change". Carmen Castro, Citizen Protection Area of the City Council of Valencia (Beaware Project).
- "Sowing Orriols" and "Orriols take the street." Manuel Tello, Orriols Convive.
- "Benicalap Más Verde". Iñaki Romero, Paisaje Transversal (Grow Green Project).
- "Valencia by the air". José Manuel Felisi, "Mesura" Platform and Environmental Technician of CAVECOVA (Confederation of Neighbourhood Associations of the Valencian Community).

Further information: <https://www.lasnaves.com/estrategias-ciudad/los-barrios-cambian-por-el-clima/?lang=es>

2019 – "VALÈNCIA CANVIA PEL CLIMA". Within the initiative called *Valencia changes by the weather*, the fair "Our light. Our energy" was organized. Several entities, social movements, NGOs, public administrations, universities and research institutes, as well as private companies met and worked together to show citizens that a new form of energy and consumption is possible. The 2019 edition of *València Canvia pel Clima!* is committed to achieve a new model of city, more humane and current, adapted to the climate change scenario. MATCHUP joined the fair.

Figure 42. VALÈNCIA CANVIA PEL CLIMA Leaflet

Further information: <https://www.lasnaves.com/energia/valencia-canvia-pel-clima-2019/?lang=es>

7 Conclusions

In this deliverable, the current state of development of the new citizens' engagement strategies in the city of Valencia has been explained, along its four main steps: ecosystem analysis, diagnosis, action plan, dissemination and communication. Some preliminary considerations are presented herewith. The main outputs of the actions and first results will be further described in the updated version of this deliverable (D2.27).

ECOSYSTEM ANALYSIS

The municipality of Valencia has been strengthening its participation infrastructure and multiplying the participatory processes in the city in the last years. The availability of such an environment eased the elaboration of new citizens' engagement strategies and may enhance any further engagement-based strategy.

Therefore, any future attempts should take into consideration and be connected to the existing participation ecosystem, while present and future actions implemented within the ecosystem should promote open access to information on the processes performed in order to enhance informed action planning and decision making, cross-fertilization, relevant stakeholders' involvement and to avoid overlapping and unnecessary overload.

DIAGNOSIS

Internal. A deep understanding of the participation level allowed by each MAtchUP action was key to establish the citizens' engagement strategy within the project. To this end, all the actions planned within the Valencia pilot site were analysed and their level of participation (informative, consultative, collaborative and empowering level) identified. The strategy for the engagement in the pilot site was therefore based on the type of participatory activities feasible according to the pilot actions features. This analytical exercise, performed individually and jointly with the Valencian pilot partners, allowed a focused, tailored and feasible strategy, avoiding false expectations in citizens that may end with low participation rates and mistrust in the future.

External. The action plan was based, as mentioned, on the very own features of each MAtchUP action, but also on a participatory diagnosis (WS3) performed in M15, involving Administration, Knowledge Transfer Centres, Companies, Citizenship and Civil Society Organizations representatives. The participatory diagnosis built on previous processes results and provided the vision of participants about how to consolidate and enhance the project impact on their Quality of Life. The results of the participatory diagnosis constitute the main action lines for the collaborative activities in the next months:

- Education and training
- Public policies & citizen engagement
- Employment and entrepreneurship

ACTION PLAN

The engagement activities within MAtchUP were planned, according to the different participation levels identified (informative, consultative, collaborative) and the participatory diagnosis (WS3) outputs.

Informative level. Several activities aimed at informing citizens about the project actions are planned. A local brand and website were created in the first place in local languages,

in order to disseminate the project actions and make them understandable in the local contest (<https://elmaritiminnova.com/>). The kick-off meeting, the participatory diagnosis, and the public presentation of the local brand and website were then performed. Accordingly, the dissemination and communication strategy enhanced these actions. Besides, visits will be realized to the demo site, allowing citizens to fully understand the actions features and implications.

Consultative level. Actions towards energy consumption and mobility, and the energy performance in private houses require the willingness of citizens to provide information. Therefore, potential users need are being identified and will be recruited, and a communication campaign deployed accordingly. Some mobility interventions also require input from neighbours in the district on needs and habits related the services offered and access to residential buildings, although specific consultative actions were not needed so far. In both cases, the understanding of the actions in the local contest is key.

Collaborative level. The objective of the collaborative participation level is to partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making. Accordingly, non-technical actions related to public policies improvement and participation, and the promotion of employment and entrepreneurship were tackled. The actions were approached as a trigger to strengthen and widen the impact of the project on the citizens' quality of life. Based on it, a group of engaged actors (organizations, public administration, companies, citizens' associations) was set up, which will act as core group and driving force along the defined action lines: education and training, employment and entrepreneurship, public policies and Open Data.

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

As shown, the dissemination and communication plan supported the citizen engagement strategy along all its phases.

8 References

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Annex I. Other relevant actors and services in the district

Public services

- SPORTS

Poliesportiu Cabanyal
Poliesportiu Beteró
Poliesportiu Dr. Lluch
Poliesportiu Nazaret

- MARKETS

Mercado Municipal del Cabanyal
Mercado Municipal del Grao
Mercado Municipal de Nazaret

- HEALTH

Centro de Salud Serrería I
Centro de Salud Vicente Brull
Centro de Salud de Nazaret
Centro de Especialidades del Grao

- CULTURAL

Biblioteca Casa de La Reina
Biblioteca Constantí Llombart
Teatre El Musical

- HEALTHCARE / SOCIAL

Centro Especializado de Atención a los Mayores
Centre Salut Mental de la Malvarrosa
Centro Ocupacional Isabel de Villena
Centro de Día de Jóvenes Malvarrosa
Centro de día de menores San Vicente Paúl en Nazaret

- OTHERS

Observatori Canvi Climàtic

Citizens and civil society organizations

- YOUTH ASSOCIATIONS

Asociación Infantil y Juvenil Nou Grup
Juniors Parroquia del Rosario
Juniors Parroquia Sta M^a Del Mar

- MUSICAL SOCIETIES

Sociedad Musical Unión de Pescadores
Sociedad Musical Poblados Marítimos
Ateneo Musical del Puerto
Coral Parroquial Virgen del Rosario del Canyamellar

- SEAFERING HOLY WEEK

Junta Mayor De La Semana Santa Marinera
Corporación de Sayones

Hermandad del Sant Cáliz de la Cena
 Santa Hermandad de la Muerte y Resurrección del Señor
 Hermandad del Stísimo Cristo del Salvador Y del Amparo
 Hermandad de María Santísima de las Angustias
 Cofradía de la Oración de Jesús en el Huerto
 Real Cofradía de Jesús en la Columna
 Germandat de la Coronació d'espines del Nostre Senyor Jesucrist
 Germandat del Santíssim Ecce-Homo
 Real Hermandad de Jesús con la Cruz y Cristo Resucitado
 Corporación de Longinos
 Hermandad del Stísimo Cristo del Perdón
 Hermandad del Stísimo Cristo del Salvador
 Corporació Granaders de la Verge
 Hermandad del Santo Silencio y Vera Cruz
 Corporación de Petrorianos Y Penitentes
 Hermandad del Santo Encuentro
 Real Hermandad de la Santa Faz
 Hermandad de la Crucifixión del Señor
 Hermandad del Stísimo Cristo de los Afligidos
 Hermandad de Vestas del Santísimo Cristo del Buen Acierto
 Cofradía de Granaderos de la Virgen de la Soledad
 Hermandad Descendimiento del Señor
 Hermandad del Santo Sepulcro
 Real Hermandad de la Flagelación del Señor
 Hermandad de Jesús De Medinaceli
 Real Hermandad de Nuestro Padre Jesús Nazareno
 Pontificia y Real Hermandad del Santísimo Cristo de la Concordia
 Hermandad Stísimo Cristo de la Palma
 Cofradía de Granaderos de la Virgen de los Dolores

- FALLAS (Municipal festivity)

Rosario - Plaza Calabuig
 Arquitecto Alfaro - Francisco Cubells
 La Cruz, Plaza - Los Angeles
 Blocs Platja
 Jose Benlliure - Teatro de La Marina
 Barraca - Trav. Iglesia Rosario
 Justo Vilar - Plaza Mercado Cabañal
 Progreso - Teatro de la Marina
 Barraca - Columbretes
 Ramon de Rocafull - Conde Alaquàs
 Vidal De Canelles - Sanchez Coello
 Jose Benlliure - Vicente Guillot
 Escalante - Marina
 Reina - Vicente Guillot
 Barraca - Espadán
 Escalante - Amparo Guillen
 Padre Luis Navarro - Remonta
 San Pedro - Virgen de Vallivana

- POLITICAL PARTIES

EUPV
 PODEMOS Círculo Marítimo

COMPROMÍS Marítim
PSPV Marítim
CIUDADANOS València
PP.CV Marítim

- RELIGIOUS

Parroquia Cristo Redentor - S. Rafael Arcángel
Parroquia Nuestra Señora de los Ángeles
Parroquia Sta. María Del Mar
Parroquia Ntra. Señora Del Rosario
Iglesia Evangélica Rey de Reyes
Iglesia Evangélica El Salvador
Iglesia Evangélica "Rúgul Aprins"

- SPORTS

Club Atletisme Poblats Marítims
Ca Running Poblats Marítims
A.D. Sociedad Deportiva Poblats Maritims
U.D. Marítimo Cabañal
Club Futbol Cabanyal Canyamelar
Club Muntanysme Maritim
Asociación Valenciana de Fútbol de Botones
Club de Hàndbol Canyamelar-Marítim
Fòrum de l'Esport

- OTHERS

Cofradía de Pescadores

